

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

CO solution mapping to pilots, recruitment and training report

Work Package 3, Deliverable D3.2

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List of Acronyms

AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)
BCC	Bristol City Council
Borghi	I Borghi piu Belli D'Italia
BUAS	Breda University of Applied Sciences
CO	Citizen Observatory
COs	Citizen Observatories
CObs	Citizen Observers
EBLN	The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood
EU	European Union
IA	Innovation Action
IAB	Innovation Action Board
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KWMC	Knowle West Media Centre
PNRR	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
PST	Pilot Support Team
UWE	University of the West of England

Glossary

Active intermediation	GREENGAGE seeks to mediate between public authorities and citizens, green initiatives, researchers, tech providers and other potential stakeholders of COs. Mediating here is the process of enabling authorities of urban policy making to democratically respond to a community’s understanding of the local needs for effective and sustainable innovation. This includes the navigation of legal and regulatory requirements, the negotiation of appropriate institutional arrangements, the mobilisation of resources and the facilitation of active participation of citizens in decision-making processes of urban planning. GREENGAGE COs will enable the active dialogue between authorities and communities by co-designed observation and analysis of real-world environments. Through active intermediation with the pilot’s situations, GREENGAGE COs will shape policy innovation in five different contexts of urban planning. Through active intermediation GREENGAGE CO coordinators aim to meet the needs of communities and serve the improvement of their well-being through the process and its outcomes (cf. May & Perry, 2017, p. 24).
Bottom-up approach on citizen science and co-creation	The GREENGAGE Innovation Action is building on a bottom-up logic on co-creation, participatory research and citizen science. We propose to draw on the established approach of Extreme Citizen Science (ExCiteS) to approach science-based, community-led policy innovation towards strong sustainability. [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]
Citizen Observatory	According to EU project WeObserve, “Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance.” [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]. In GREENGAGE, CO is a place like a <i>Living Lab</i> (a laboratory in a real context, putting stakeholders at the centre of the process) for collective learning that exploits the opportunity of using sensors and the use of Earth observation technology where citizens collect data and are empowered by the information generated from these data to improve environmental management towards an innovative governance of the territory.
Citizen Science	“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).
Citizen Science campaign	A Citizen Science (CS) Campaign comprises a period when a group of Citizen Observers with a shared mission and hypothesis gather data at different places and regularly get together to analyse together the correlation of their collected data with other external data sources to validate such hypothesis.
GREEN Engine	The GREENGAGE Engine is the set of tools and software applications that make up the GREENGAGE toolset. They will be used to support the GREENGAGE COs in fulfilling the objectives of the Innovation Pilots.
Innovation Actions	Innovation Actions are "primarily consisting of activities directly aiming at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. For this purpose, they may include prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication. [...] Projects may include limited research and development activities” (EU HORIZON 2020). For GREENGAGE COs this means participatory research for

	innovation is not the focus but a means for understanding the GREENGAGE Innovation Action collectively.
Living Labs	According to the European Network of Living Labs, “Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders.”
Pilot Owner	The city or authority responsible for the implementation of a particular GREENGAGE innovation pilot.
Situational onboarding of CO participants	Situational onboarding conceptualises the GREENGAGE engagement methodology. Situational onboarding is sensitive to context, time, capacities and other variables that impact on the ability of citizens to actively participate in COs. It seeks to meet people where they are, be inclusive, and extend and diversify the contributions of participants at different stages of the co-creation process. The methodology suggests reflexive questions as a tool for develop engagement strategies with the different pilot partners.
The GREENGAGE Academy	The GREENGAGE Academy hosts the emerging GREENGAGE Community of Practise and is the central platform for sharing understandings of the process of developing GREENGAGE COs. As such, the Academy serves as the central interaction platform between CO coordinators, Citizen Observers and other participants of COs. The Academy acts as a knowledge base around the setting up and effective coordination of citizen observatories. The Academy stores and indexes training resources, MOOCs, success stories, findings and best practises collected from the four GREENGAGE pilots as well as generated or adapted to guide the setting up of the pilots.
The GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory Methodological Framework	The GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory (CO) methodological framework suggests core concepts, processes and guidelines on how to develop COs in GREENGAGE in ways that are ethical, democratic and responsive to common urban challenges and their situational manifestations in five pilots.
Thematic Co-Explorations	A Thematic Co-Exploration involves a group of people that combines already available datasets (Open Data, Copernicus) with those datasets that Citizen Observers can contribute with. The idea is that heterogenous datasets are combined and correlated to give place to indicators and visualisations that are widely understandable by laypeople. Besides, the conclusions or insights driven by each pilot will be mapped into storylines, i.e., narrative, and visual communication to raise awareness about the issues associated to Green Deal and possible solutions that as society we can tackle.
Top-down approach on policy innovation	The GREENGAGE Innovation Action is informed by a top-down logic. That means the developed frameworks are setting boundaries for meaningful experimentation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ethical framework is defining procedures on how to apply ethics in GREENGAGE COs. • The governance framework is defining the metrics through which the innovation potential of pilots will be captured. • The methodological framework is setting core concepts and guides the development of the GREENGAGE approach on COs. • The citizen science methodology frames how CO campaigns will be co-designed and co-delivered through exploring and exploiting existing technologies in piloting COs. [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]
Use cases	Generally, use cases are specific situations in which a product or service could potentially be used. In GREENGAGE we experiment in place-based, co-created

	<p>and living platforms and learn about the useability of REENGAGE COs as mediators of urban policy innovation. The products that are tested on their usefulness for driving transformative urban planning are existing technologies, tools and practices that brought into play by the REENGAGE consortium to build tech-aided and co-created environmental monitoring and information systems, or REENGAGE COs.</p>
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Executive summary (publishable)

This report documents the alignment of the GREENGAGE CO Methodological framework with the specificities of pilot cities and the preparation and activation of recruitment and training activities. The report describes GREENGAGE’s solutions to respond to the distinct features of each pilot city by tailoring enabling solutions to pilots’ context while seeking replicable outcomes. As described in the GREENGAGE CO methodological framework, the report focuses on how the project carried out active intermediation during the preparation phase and set the ground for the forthcoming piloting phase. The report describes: a) the organisational structure, processes and tools put together to respond to the changing situation in the pilots and bring innovation to urban policy-making by utilising digital solutions to engage citizens, b) the process by which a comprehensive understanding of relevant contextual information of each pilot was developed following a situational analysis c) the process of drawing a GREENGAGE roadmap outlining how CO initiatives will be carried out in each city d) How recruitment and training were conceptualised and operationalised as situational onboarding in preparation of the piloting phase.

Related documents

Deliverable D2.1 – GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework.

Deliverable 3.3 – GREENGAGE CO Academy Roadmap.

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes and help public authorities shape their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project will leverage citizens' participation and equip them with innovative digital solutions to foster citizens' engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon-neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories will be where pilot cities will co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up processes with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The envisioned citizens observatory campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Object of the Deliverable

This report offers a comprehensive overview of how the GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework was mapped to suit the pilot's specificities and how it informed the preparation and activation of the pilot's CO's recruitment and training activities.

The GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework proposes a distinctive approach to co-creation, situational onboarding of participants, and guidelines to coordinate the development of GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab. This report covers tasks 3.1 (Mapping GREENGAGE CO-enabling solution to Pilots context) and 3.3 (Recruit teams of Citizen Observers for Pilots), where concepts, processes, approaches and guidelines, defined as part of the Methodological Framework, were applied and adapted in the light of opening the recruitment and training process while acknowledging the pilot's specificities and ensuring compliance with ethical environmental, social, cultural, political, privacy, and data ownership guidelines.

Together with deliverables 3.1 (Citizen Observer Training: "How to do research" and CO toolbox) and 3.3 (GREENGAGE CO Academy Roadmap), this report feeds the GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory Academy. It provides the first evidence of how GREENGAGE apply Living Lab and citizen science-based solutions to address the unique challenges and opportunities of the diverse Pilot cities.

3 Introduction

The GREENGAGE project aims to enhance governance for climate mitigation and adaptation policies by involving citizens in co-creating green initiatives and developing Citizen Observatories (COs) focusing on mobility, air quality, and healthy living. In the GREENGAGE project, Citizen Observatories are community-based environmental monitoring systems that encourage individuals to share observations and interpretations through digital solutions to address pan-European urban and regional planning challenges.

As a pan-European research Innovation Action, GREENGAGE is committed to experimental learning and collaboration, sharing insights and recommendations. In accordance with the Horizon IA definition, within the context of the project, an Innovation Action (IA) is described as a research initiative predominantly centred on practical endeavours aimed at formulating plans, designs, or enhancements in products, processes, or services. The project focuses on transformative urban policymaking, utilising digital solutions to engage citizens and improve cities' effectiveness in achieving European Green Deal objectives. In the case of GREENGAGE, the IA approach relies on participatory research to collectively understand and support the overall Innovation Action.

GREENGAGE COs are grounded on citizen science principles by which public engagement in scientific research fosters collaboration between lay citizens and professional researchers, contributing to a more democratic research environment. GREENGAGE COs aim to make knowledge and policy production more transparent, fostering trust in scientific practices and generating insights to address urban challenges amidst the ongoing climate crisis.

In the GREENGAGE COs, participatory research is employed to democratise urban knowledge production. Making urban knowledge production more inclusive, participatory, and accessible implies involving a broader range of participants in collective learning and highlighting the interpretations and perspectives of those actively shaping political experiments within the community in shaping urban policies and innovations. The GREENGAGE Academy serves as a platform for continuous learning and altering the understanding of conditions for knowledge co-production. The project advocates for collective learning grounded in reflexivity, emphasising the active involvement of participants in shaping political experiments for democratic policy innovation.

The project's methodological framework understands the development of COs as a living lab, aligning with the European Network of Living Labs and emphasising open innovation ecosystems, co-creation, rapid prototyping, testing, and scaling up innovations. The Citizen Observatories (COs) are treated as Living Labs where real-world scenarios serve as platforms for research and development activities, allowing for testing existing technologies, tools, and practices in developing COs.

As Living Labs, COs are mediators between public authorities and citizens, researchers, tech providers, and other stakeholders. The mediatory process involves enabling urban policymakers to respond democratically to community needs, navigating legal and regulatory requirements, and facilitating the active participation of citizens in decision-making processes. COs enable a dialogue between authorities and communities through co-designed observation and analysis of real-world environments, generating new datasets through citizen involvement and allowing stakeholders to interpret and design local policies adaptive to climate change.

GREENGAGE's methodological framework emphasises continuous learning, responding to changing situations in the pilots, and building a conceptual foundation for comparison and mutual learning across locations (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. The GREENGAGE process for developing GREENGAGE COs as a Living Lab

Developing the COs involves three continuous stages of experimentation: preparing, piloting, and collective learning, which relate directly to the conceptualisation and sharing activities.

By **preparing**, we mean agreeing on the concepts and process for structuring GREENGAGE's governance concerning building communities of practice and co-designing tools and technologies. It also involves planning the COs' activation before implementation. The preparation phase defines three initial steps necessary to launch a GREENGAGE CO: (a) the (preliminary) top-down definition of the objectives of the CO, (b) the analysis of the current situation of the pilot owner in relation to all aspects and/or dimensions that are relevant for the launch and subsequent operation of the CO, and (c) the creation (mapping, engaging and gathering) of the first community of citizens that will participate in the CO, called Citizen Observers. **Piloting** is the process in which the COs carry out their research activities, involving prototyping, testing, monitoring, gathering data, and making sense of data together with participants of COs. **Collective Learning** addresses the reflexive activities in which participants of the

experiments bring about their interpretation and knowledge production to address new, more nuanced or reformulated shared concerns and the conceptual architecture from which they emerge.

In this manner, the GREENGAGE CO methodology proposes an initial set of processes and principles to inform a specific use of it according to the different contextual realities of the different pilots involved in the project. More than a set of steps it suggests a path to be adapted and enriched by the collaborative practices guiding the COs as Living Labs.

This report describes how the GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework was aligned to the pilots' specificities and how, in consequence, the recruitment and training activities were started. As described in the methodology, this report thus focuses on how the project carried out active intermediation during the preparation phase and how it set the ground for the forthcoming piloting phase.

3.1 Mapping solutions, recruitment and training

A core element of the methodology is mapping CO solutions to pilots, which is the process of aligning the GREENGAGE CO methodology to the specific conditions of each pilot city, while considering a wide range of factors and defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the impact of planned actions in a way that is sensitive to the diverse contextual realities of each location.

Each pilot city in the GREENGAGE project has its distinct characteristics. These include demographic factors (such as population distribution and immigration patterns), political and socioeconomic factors, and other sociological considerations. Due to the uniqueness of each pilot, it is challenging to achieve completely replicable outcomes in different contexts, cities, regions, or countries. It also implies keeping an eye on different needs in terms of recruitment needed training in preparation for the piloting phase.

Task 3.1 (Mapping GREENGAGE CO-enabling solution to Pilots' context) addresses the challenge of customising the GREENGAGE CO methodology to the specific needs of each pilot by a) Developing a comprehensive understanding of relevant contextual information of each pilot, including demographic, political, and socioeconomic factors; b) Ensuring the adapted methodology adheres to ethical, environmental, social, cultural, political, privacy, and data ownership guidelines; c) Defining KPIs to ensure egalitarian participation and non-discrimination in CS-based experiments; and, d) Defining a GREENGAGE roadmap outlining how CO initiatives will be carried out in each city, which lessons can be learned, and identifying the peculiarities of each pilot and joint actions supporting outcomes' applicability in other locations.

GREENGAGE's approach was to do a situational analysis to understand the relevant contextual information and addressing the tension between top-down and bottom-up trajectories in this Innovation Action. In such an approach, the situation is the unit of analysis, and particular attention is given to diversity of all kinds amidst human and non-human actors, like technological solutions (Clarke et al., 2022). Mapping solutions to pilots thus was understood and implemented as the process of intermediation between pilots' situations and the task and objectives of the GREENGAGE project.

Task 3.3 (Recruit teams of Citizen Observers for Pilots) was implemented in such a light and involved a) identifying teams of potential Citizen Observers and b) inviting the potential participants to join the Citizens Observatories. In coherence with the methodology and unlike traditional recruitment, the project defined recruitment as situational onboarding. This onboarding is a notion involving an ongoing process of citizen engagement, considering retention and participants' specific circumstances. Situational onboarding is context-sensitive, addressing variables like time and capacities. It aims to be inclusive, extending contributions from various participants in co-creation processes, including citizens, project partners, and other stakeholders. This report describes how such tasks were carried out by designing and implementing a screening process, situational analysis and an activation plan alongside developing a roadmap for active intermediation of the project.

3.2 Description of the pilots

Copenhagen (Ørestad)

Ørestad stands out as a unique district situated southwest of Copenhagen's city centre on Amager Island and adjacent to the 'Common' nature reserve. Comprising a blend of residential, commercial, and educational structures, including facilities for Law, Humanities, and IT University, each sector accommodates approximately 20,000 residents.

The practical implementation in Ørestad revolves around the liveability of neighbourhoods' life, air and noise quality and a nuanced understanding of how different places and streets are utilised across the neighbourhood. The pilot aims to collect a validated local data set that supports creating a local citizen-centric traffic infrastructure plan for the district of Amager West in Copenhagen.

The project will use participatory data collection to produce a recognised and validated data set as a basis for professional planning and democratic debate. It will invite residents and commuters (organised citizens, individuals, and businesses) to collect data and design more sustainable local solutions. The pilot aims to use GREENGAGE Engine tools and third-party apps to measure air and noise quality, identify residents' and commuters' perceptions, and identify where people spend time in public spaces, the number of cars passing at selected streets, and other variables of urban fabric (e.g., trees). The pilot envisions a local traffic plan worked into the city's traffic plan, where the existing infrastructure will be redefined towards less emissions and better local quality.

Bristol

The Liveable Neighbourhood programme, envisioned by Bristol City Council, aims to empower local communities in transforming their neighbourhoods into places that provide better access to green and recreational spaces, more seamless and convenient connections to local amenities using sustainable forms of travel, and more space for social and community activities. The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) pilot is located in the inner east of Bristol, a geographical area of 1.7 square kilometres housing approximately 6000 properties and businesses. Having progressed through the Co-Discover and Co-Design stages, EBLN is now transitioning into the Trial stage. Bristol is actively monitoring and evaluating the impacts of interventions to understand the effects within the inner part of the designated area to validate the positive outcomes for residents. During this phase, GREENGAGE will provide valuable insights that will guide decision-making for implementing permanent interventions in the subsequent stages of the initiative.

The EBLN pilot aims, in collaboration with organised citizens, residents of the pilot area, seldom-heard communities and public institutions, to make use of the GREENGAGE Engine and other third party apps to i) analyse and visualise the impact of road closures on mobility patterns (journey quality); ii) monitor and visualise air quality and noise levels iii) Monitor environment and identify road safety/threat levels iv) determine the routes that citizens take to local amenities and identify areas for potential improvements.

The pilot's comprehensive approach aims to a) uncover and address mobility disparities, ultimately creating a more equitable and balanced transportation landscape, b) establish a robust case for the long-term implementation of measures that enhance the local environment, ensuring the well-being of the community, c) empower communities and citizens to actively contribute to the enhancement and policymaking and implementation of road safety and more efficient and accessible mobility solutions.

North-Brabant

The province of North Brabant is situated in the southern region of the Netherlands. Collaborating with central and decentralised government entities, including 56 municipalities, the local organisation serves nearly 2.6 million regional residents. The province envisions a transition to sustainable traffic and transport as a key objective to address significant challenges such as urbanisation, traffic safety, health,

inclusivity, and economic and energy challenges. A central focus within this vision is the promotion of cycling, aiming for a 20% increase in cycled kilometres by 2027 and a 40% increase by 2040.

The province has identified three major focus points to achieve these goals: cycling infrastructure, bicycle parking, and stimulation activities. The North Brabant pilot is structured around these objectives. Collaborating with the expertise of Breda University of Applied Sciences (BUAS), the pilot adopts a two-phase approach, gathering both quantitative data (mobility patterns, bike routes, modal split) and qualitative data (decision-making processes).

The pilot intends to use the GREENGAGE Engine with other technological tools to i) analyse multimodal travel patterns in collaboration with commuters and travellers to assess bikeable routes and areas ii) investigate the decision-making process regarding the transportation modality to identify deterrents for bike usage in collaboration with people who can bike but currently do not, avid bike and car users and usually underrepresented groups. The pilot approach aims to unravel the decision-making processes and barriers associated with transportation choices, contributing to more sustainable and informed mobility solutions.

Gerace and Turano Valley

Gerace is a town in the Province of Reggio Calabria, in the Region of Calabria, which extends over 28.6 km² and has 2.399 inhabitants. The Turano Valley is in the province of Rieti in the Lazio region, crossed by the Turano River. The valley is home to Turano Lake, an artificial basin created in the 1930s for hydroelectric power. Collalto Sabino, Castel di Tora, Paganico Sabino, and Ascrea are the primary municipalities within the Turano Valley.

Both pilot areas, under the coordination of the Italian Association of the Most Beautiful Villages in Italy (Borghi Più Belli d'Italia), aim to study people's mobility and promote urban revitalisation in support of the objectives of the EU Green Deal for sustainable city regeneration in synergy with an ongoing EU Next Generation fund for the EU recovery and resilience plan.

In collaboration with public institutions, academia, professional experts, NGO and third sector groups, private enterprises and citizens, the pilot seeks to i) improve local strategies on infrastructure and mobility services, ii) Address progressive depopulation of the villages, iii) Promote urban revitalisation. With the help of the GREEN engine and third-party apps, the pilot aims to collect reliable and detailed data about mobility, air quality, noise level and other environmental and health variables for the new mobility and quality of life plan in Gerace and urban planning and transport management in Turano Valley.

4 Developing GREENGAGE Citizens Observatories Structure

4.1 Organisational Structure for Supporting the Citizens' Observatories

The experimental learning and collaboration at the core of GREENGAGE as an Innovation Action is reflected in the instituted organisational structure to prepare and activate the COs. This structure is intended to intermediate between the top-down frames of action and the bottom-up local situation of pilots. As depicted in Figure 3, the structure sets two intertwined bodies acting at different scales: a) the pilot Support Teams (PSTs) working on the local situation of pilots and b) the Innovation Action Board, overseeing the GREENGAGE Innovation Action. The description of their role and functions are written down in the working documents “Clear-UP: How We Approach Co-creation” and “Definition of Pilot Support Team (PST) and Innovation Action Board (IAB) WP3”.

4.1.1 Pilot Support Team (PST)

The pilot Support Teams (PSTs) are interdisciplinary groups of partner representatives that assist the five pilot initiatives in developing their use cases and foster the constitution of functioning GREENGAGE COs as Living Labs. The PSTs shall achieve a deeper understanding of the local necessities and support in-depth discussions on technical solutions and social enablers accordingly. PSTs are the local operational link with Pilots and aim to foster feedback and responsiveness to ensure the development of the COs.

The Pilot Support Teams are designed to facilitate each phase of the Innovation Action. Key focus areas of the PST include assistance in clarifying a) the mission and vision of CO, b) the process of co-creation, c) Ethics guidelines and procedures, d) onboarding activities, e) exploring and exploiting existing tech, f) generating, managing, analysing & telling stories with data g) collaborating & learning across GREENGAGE COs.

Figure 3. Communication between COs, PSTs and IAB

The GREENGAGE IA is composed of five (5) Pilot Support teams (Bristol, Copenhagen, North Brabant, Turano and Gerace) each with approximately 10 members from the different partners.

Each PST consists of:

- Two PST leaders (one from the social sciences domain one from the technology team, chosen by the project coordinator) in charge of organising the PST and its proceedings.
- At least one additional partner with social science expertise is included to assist in participative and co-creative processes.
- A additional partner able to assist in fitting the chosen technological solution to the pilot's use cases and who can also provide additional technical support if needed.
- When possible, the PST also tries to bring together members with pertinent language skills needed within the pilot.

4.1.2 Innovation Action Board (IAB)

The Innovation Action Board (IAB) is a collaborative and interdisciplinary team comprising partner representatives that oversees the whole GREENGAGE IA and steers the PSTs. As depicted in Figure 4, the IAB offers backend assistance to pilot projects and ensures the replicability of the GREENGAGE approach across COs.

The IAB operates with a clearly defined standard information flow and feedback loop for optimal efficiency. One of the crucial responsibilities of IAB members is actively providing feedback on partners' drafts of generic models, ensuring the incorporation of all essential perspectives for interdisciplinary co-production of knowledge assets.

The IAB comprises members drawn from the PSTs, with some redundancy accounted for. It concentrates on colleagues involved in citizen engagement within the pilots, and it includes pertinent members from the entire GREENGAGE team, encompassing key technical partners possessing expertise in technology and citizen participation.

Some of the critical functions of the IAB are: a) Methodological conceptualisation and validation of the GREENGAGE approach on COs, b) Encouraging pilots' collective learning and sharing, c) Ensuring that Planio and the Collaborative Environment as platforms for R&D of the GREENGAGE as Innovation Action are understood, maintained & used for that purpose by all participants that take part in learning within the Innovation Action, d) Build up close connections & peer learning opportunities with EU sister projects.

Figure 4. Overview of PSTs, IAB, and platforms to be used

4.2 Basic process for orienting Co-design of Citizens Observatories

A basic process was proposed to contribute to the preparation stage of the GREENGAGE COs. The steps are:

- Starting situational screening of pilots.
- Co-designing of the GREENGAGE CO Academy Roadmap.
- Co-producing the CO toolbox (delivering onboarding and training materials for pilot partners that are developing GREENGAGE COs).
- Activating COs through a plan (Activation plan) for the onboarding participants (citizens and other local stakeholders).

A basic procedure was proposed to prepare onboarding and training materials. It outlines how the IAB and the PSTs interact in preparing recruitment and training materials specifically for COs.

For the onboarding phases the project defined the following:

- The IAB prepares the situational analysis. This phase implies defining what information is needed to prepare onboarding (screening questionnaire) for each pilot's situation using as reference GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework.
- The PSTs carry out the situation analysis and an activation plan. The engagement partners brief the PST leads to moderate the interdisciplinary situational analysis. The expected outcome is to be able to define an engagement methodology to each pilot's situation.

- The IAB, in line with the ethics guidelines including Participant Information Sheet (PIS), Participant Consent Form (PCF), delivers strategic guidance on generic onboarding surveys needed in the onboarding phase to focus on pro-environmental and mobility behaviour.
- The PSTs and Pilot Owners translate onboarding and training documents into the pilot's local language.

For the co-production of the training material the following phases were defined:

- The IAB gathers existing knowledge assets relevant to setting up GREENGAGE COs. This includes valuable data quality and visualisation training material available from best EU practices identified by the projects such as WeObserve, an H2020 Coordination and Support Action (CSA) gathering four different observatory projects, and its toolkit (<https://www.weobserve.eu/toolkit/>).
- The PSTs define the state of knowledge about the specific use cases and develop interdisciplinary problem statements for each pilot. Decide what existing knowledge assets are relevant for setting up the pilot's COs and request modification if these are not useful, yet. The also develop training materials and manuals for the pilot platforms.

Whilst several GREENGAGE tasks and activities were running concurrently, it was observed that to simplify the sheer complexity of setting up and running COs, there is a need to build a common understanding within the multi-disciplinary GREENGAGE team. Further, there was a general feeling that GREENGAGE should clearly define the process of COs' involvement in the GREENGAGE COs with possible activities they might be engaged in. Similarly, there was a need to define what are different stages Pilot Owners will have to go through to fully setup, realise, evaluate and benefit from the outcomes of COs.

With the abovementioned rationale, a so-called Citizen Observer Journey was designed. After introducing its first version, a collaborative approach was adopted where all GREENGAGE partners were invited to co-design the COs Journey. Like COs Journey, a first version of the Pilot Owners' Journey was prepared followed by a collaborative approach to co-design it. GREENGAGE partners were invited to co-design the stages and activities expected by Pilot Owners via a generic perspective. Several comments were received which resulted in a general refined version of COs Journey as depicted in Figure 5. The COs' Journey presents a generic approach and is currently fully adapted to each of the pilots' contexts.

Both Journey models (Citizen Observers' and draft version of Pilot Owners') were used to translate the CO Methodological Framework into GREENGAGE's Collaborative Environment. Originally developed by the INTERLINK project, this tool is undergoing expansion in GREENGAGE to facilitate and empower collaborative efforts in the thematic co-explorations conducted within Citizen Observatories (CO). The Collaborative Environment within GREENGAGE provides a digital space that can streamline co-production interactions among public administrations, private stakeholders, and citizens. It encourages the reuse of software and knowledge assets to enhance the provision of public services. In GREENGAGE, diverse participants can collaborate, accessing the necessary knowledge and tools to collectively contribute to the design and delivery of services or artefacts.

The preparation of the piloting also involved adapting the existing logic of the Collaborative Environment to the stages of the Bristol Approach to Citizens' Sensing. This is a people-led approach to co-creation that brings together technologies and city inhabitants around six iterative stages: identifying, framing, designing, testing, sharing and reflecting. The Pilot Owner Journey and Citizen Observer Journey were also adapted to the Collaborative Environment to help project partners streamline the development of the Citizen Observatories. The exchange of information on this platform should help the consortium partners to co-create and document the GREENGAGE Innovation Action and nurture the GREENGAGE Academy.

GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

Citizen Observers (CObs) can join the journey at any stage after completing the Onboarding (Ethics) requirements

Privacy and data anonymisation are essential before reporting or publishing outcomes

CObs may not be involved in all stages, but consent allows withdrawal at any stage
Anonymized and aggregated data may be non-withdrawable

CITIZEN OBSERVERS JOURNEY

~15 minutes

1 GREENGAGE OBSERVERS ONBOARDING

2-4 hours

2 TRAINING TO BECOME CITIZEN OBSERVER

+8 hours

3 EXPERIMENTS AND DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

+8 hours

5 EVALUATION & IMPACT ASSESSMENT

4 DATA ANALYSIS & VISUALISATION

6 CITIZENS USE GREENGAGE CO OUTCOMES

INITIATE OTHER LOCAL ACTIONS

CONTRIBUTE TO POLICY MAKING AND POLICY EVALUATION

Figure 5. Citizen Observer Journey

5 Developing the CO solution mapping to pilots

5.1 Situational Screening

The design and completion of the screening questionnaire were the initial steps in tailoring the methodology to the specificities of each pilot. The questionnaire was crafted to facilitate a guided information-gathering process on the requirements of the Innovation Pilots. It aimed to assist in planning the creation of the first community of Citizen Observers while considering the pilot's current situation in terms of organisation, engagement, technology, and communication.

The questionnaire was developed using Situational Analysis as a theoretical and methodological reference, an approach that identifies the situation as a specific unit of analysis to unravel complex relations of human and non-human elements. Drawing partially from the field of science and technology studies, Situational Analysis considers the role material elements have in shaping interactions among actors, how people communicate with each other, and what discursive and institutional structure constrains or enables relations under the situation deemed relevant to understand (Clarke et al., 2022).

The questionnaire (see Annex A) drew inspiration from several sources, including D2.1 GREENGAGE COs Methodological Framework; D2.2 Use Cases and Requirement Analysis I; D2.4 Smart Governance Models 1; brainstorming outcomes from several consortium meetings, and the Community-Based Initiative (CPI) Framework developed within the GROUNDTRUTH project. The CPI framework aims to analyse the dynamics underlying the establishment and functioning of "community-based initiatives" (similar to COs) by gathering information on context-related factors through different questions. It is suitable for "Situational analysis," "Process evaluation," and "Impact assessment" of the initiatives.

The questionnaire pursued a dual objective. On the one hand, to support the performance of a situational screening of the innovation pilots, to be undertaken by the pilot owners. On the other hand, to start a situational analysis to define a strategy for the pilot owners to make the necessary adaptations to move forward in the CO conceptualisation stage (see Annex B).

The questionnaire was defined during several rounds of collaborative work with the consortium partners. It inquired five key dimensions deemed relevant to setting up and executing COs: (1) goals and objectives; (2) political, institutional, and power dynamics; (3) technological; (4) public engagement; and (5) sociodemographic dimensions. The questions serve as a support tool to promote self-reflection and understanding of each innovation pilot's current situation. The questionnaire was designed to link conceptualisation and preparation activities for setting up a CO and paid particular attention to an intersectional approach.

The goals and objectives dimension (3 questions) focused on facilitating the self-assessment regarding the connection of the Citizen Observers with the objectives of the innovation pilot to address the tension between top-down predefined overarching objectives and bottom-up locally informed concerns.

The political, institutional, and power dynamics dimension (8 questions) encompassed questions regarding (a) policies and decision-making frameworks within which the CO might operate, (b) the formal and informal structures, rules, and norms that will guide the functioning of the CO, and (c) the power dynamics that connect the objectives, functioning, and results of the initiatives of each innovation pilot.

The technological dimension (6 questions) explored the set of technologies (from the GREEN Engine and other communication technologies and channels) that each innovation pilot envisions using and how.

The public engagement dimension (6 questions) sought to align local debates, engaged communities, and existing participatory initiatives with the COs' thematic concerns.

The socio-demographic dimensions examined intersectionality in the pilots' municipalities, striving for equality regarding representation among different groups (number of inhabitants, characteristics of the area in terms of age, gender, origin, disability, social class and educational level in the CO action area).

Pilot owners received the questionnaires and were encouraged to fill them in consultation with different experts within the pilot owners' organisation. Their answer received a round of comments from members of the pilot Support Teams to foster the collaborative analysis of the information.

The screening questionnaires provided a broad source of information and signalled situational differences between the pilots, as well as coherence with the general objectives of the project. It

informed the situational analysis, helped narrow thematic co-explorations, clarified impact policy fields, and suggested potential sources for pertinent indicators in each pilot.

5.2 Situational Analysis for CO Activation

The situational analyses for the CO Activation used the Bristol Approach to structure the analysis. The Bristol approach is a co-creation approach involving six stages: i) identifying ii) framing iii) designing iv) testing v) sharing vi) reflecting. Identifying and framing guided the analysis as intended to identify the key issues that people care about and the key participants around shared goals that frame the future planned activities of the COs. The first analysis stage proposed a collective exercise of building a “messy situational map” as a Miro workshop. Messy situational maps lay out all the major human, nonhuman, discursive, historical, symbolic, cultural, political and other elements found in the research situation to enable a relational analysis of different elements that matter in the situation and to guide interdisciplinary research and data gathering.

The workshop aimed to clarify the relations between actors and spaces needed in the Observatory core group using the information compiled in the screening questionnaire. As part of the analysis, communication and relationships between the different locations of actors (like public administration) were taken into account to allow situational onboarding actions to ensure inclusion and diversity. The messy map worked as a method to visualise the information in an early analysis stage.

The questionnaires' output also helped inform Citizen Observatory Journeys, driven by a co-creation process to be implemented to setup the CO. The journey included a general description where the main features of each local situation were reported in conjunction with the technical solutions and their relation to specific use cases identified in each pilot through Planio. Such a document gave GREENGAGE a comprehensive perspective of each pilot regarding their social and technological needs. It included the following per pilot: a) Use case definitions b) Objectives c) A CO-creation collaborative process description d) Data perspective e) Technological perspective f) Analytical perspective g) Public engagement perspective.

The situational analysis continued as part of the activities of the second consortium meeting, where each pilot team got together in a dedicated session to update the pilot situation and inform the future development of the CO Academy Roadmap. Some of the relevant findings for each pilot in the face of future onboarding activities were the overview of the political context in each pilot, the possible policy impact field, the definition of target groups and the selection of technological tools available for the CO development.

A summary of the sessions per pilot was presented in the plenary of the meeting consortium. The most relevant themes that arose having in mind the CO Academy Roadmap per pilot were:

North Brabant:

- They have planned a 2-phased approach for the CO: first (quantitative) with a focus on data gathering; second (qualitative) data gathering and interpretation (training should thus accompany the two phases).
- Clear target groups emphasising people with international backgrounds, parents taking care of children, and people in mobility poverty (with no mobility options).
- The pilot’s DigiTwin visualisation maps allow seeing blind spots, providing a good starting point. The pilot wants to identify the possibilities and new features the GREENGAGE app could provide.
- They see a policy change from the intervention level (small scale, like business/university policies).

Bristol:

- The existing EBLN approach to the co-creation of Bristol City Council was convergent with the GREENGAGE approach to co-creation.

- Despite the political uncertainty (a committee at the City Council level will replace the Mayor), Vivacity ¹sensors are being installed in early November to capture traffic data (e.g., speed, maps of mobility, vehicle class).
- A baseline dataset is already available through the Liveable Neighbourhood programme. The Liveable Neighbourhood's geographical and population focus reflects the Equality Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) ethical principles.

Copenhagen:

- Expresses a desire to engage with employees of local companies to participate in the COs.
- Need to start early to benefit from the climate conditions before Winter to map the use of public spaces.
- On the technical side, the pilot defined the relation with their dedicated Copenhagen app, how to connect it to the GREENGAGE back end, and the sensors and hardware to use for the data collection.
- Strengthening the intended use of the data beyond the feedback and use for citizens participating in the CO.

Gerace and Turano Valley:

- Gerace identified a scenario for the policy innovation of the mobility plan for the municipality.
- They have an interest in better analysis of the mobility phenomena (summer in particular), air pollution, and quality of life; b) Visualisation potential, engage people to improve the visualisation (e.g., satellite data) c) See the trust of data in different stakeholders (depending on the source).
- They have already identified target groups interested: The general public, small companies, non-profit associations/organisations, and academia. For other stakeholders, we need to discover their interests first.
- Need a dedicated GREENGAGE pilot webpage to facilitate continuous interaction.

As a result, it was possible to identify the interest in researching the quality of air, mobility and use of public spaces as main themes to be addressed by pilots. These thematic co-explorations are frames that allow the development of the specificities of each pilot under common themes.

The situational analysis also allowed us to identify meaningful differences in terms of:

Exposure to uncertainty: The exposure to risks due to the political situation is higher in Bristol, where the city council and the trajectory of Liveable Neighbourhood have a heavyweight. Along the same line, the government's transition process in Gerace impacted the pace of the pilot process.

Institutional embeddedness: The institutional structure, where each pilot owner is immersed, provides differential enablers and barriers for the future activation phase. Bristol and North Brabant, who already have co-creation and participatory processes in place, implied a differential approach in terms of adapting and fostering their practices to the GREENGAGE CO Framework. A similar situation can be found in Copenhagen, where the pilot has extensive expertise with a longstanding and carefully developed group of participants. Different is the case of Gerace and Turano Valley, who, while having long experience in a participatory process, are interested in enhancing the science and data-related capacities for political innovation.

Relation with public authorities: While some pilots (Bristol and North Brabant) are embedded in the municipal or regional authorities respectively, others are in between administrative levels (Borghi) with close links to municipal powers but are closely related to them. Others are outside such a structure (Copenhagen). The differential position is relevant for the communication with public authorities and the identity of the Citizen Observatory as such.

¹ <https://vivacitylabs.com/>

The information gathered as part of the situational analysis was informed and updated in the Citizen Observatory Journeys and was considered when developing the CO Academy roadmap, where the preparation of the recruitment and training activities started.

In line with the basic co-creation process, the consortium needed to transform the situation analysis' outcome into an actionable plan to activate future Citizen Observers. The outcome aimed to be shaped into an activation plan. The plan aimed at: 1. Identify the stakeholders to be involved in the CO. 2. Develop training materials. 3. Create fiches for the GREENGAGE Engine technologies. 4. Set up a facilitator team within the pilot owner. 5. Create an engagement plan, including a draft of the communication strategy. In practice, the activation plan was drafted as part of the workshops and discussion of the CO Academy Road mapping described in section 6.1 reporting on the situational onboarding activities.

5.3 Definition of pilot specific KPIs

The screening questionnaire and situational analysis also resulted in a first approximation of possible sources for the KPIs in each pilot thematic co-exploration. Questions 14 to 16 aimed at identifying already used data sources to monitor policies, missing datasets that could be used and current analysis capacities. Some preliminary sources were identified, considering the future construction of tailor indicators for each pilot political incidence aim.

Bristol: The pilot is embedded in the Bristol City Council's vision for the Liveable Neighbourhood programme (EBLN): to empower local communities to transform their neighbourhoods into places which provide better access to green and play space, more seamless and convenient connections to local amenities using sustainable forms of travel, and more space for social and community activity. The EBLN is aligned to a greater extent with the EU-selected Green Deals' areas of GREENGAGE, and possible indicators can be built on their existing monitoring and evaluation tools and datasets as described in it. Other relevant policies, strategies, and guidance identified were a) Gear change: a bold vision for cycling and walking (publishing.service.gov.uk) b) Local Transport Note 1/20 c) Joint Local Transport Plan 4 d) West of England Climate Emergency Action Plan e) West of England Bus Service Improvement Plan f) Local Cycling and Walking Improvement Plan g) Bristol Transport Strategy h) One City Climate Strategy i) One City Plan.

North Brabant: The pilot identified as possible sources for KPIs: a) the Datasets from the B-Riders project, a project in which the Province of North Brabant joined forces with business and industry to get employees to switch from car to bicycle use. The project already gave a quantitative overview of where people from the province biked and with which motivations. b) Other sources are the datasets of municipal mobility counting sensors (ViNotion, Rezonon cameras) that can map traffic flows in different province cities.

Turano: The situational analysis identified the Mobility, Transport and Logistics Plan (PRMTL) as the primary regional planning tool in the Lazio region and a possible reference for the pilot objectives. The plan is drawn up in collaboration with the State, the Regions and Rome authorities and includes the several main quantitative objectives set by the European Union. Along the same line, at a regional level, there is an open data portal (<https://dati.lazio.it/>) and various data from other sources, starting from ISTAT.

Other relevant information for defining KPIs was identifying underrepresented groups in the pilot area. Some pilots, like Bristol, had a geographical identification of underrepresented groups aligned with the approach institutionalised within the Liveable Neighbourhood programme. For other pilots like North Brabant and based on their work in the Cycling Lab, underrepresented groups were identified as inhabitants with international backgrounds and those who do not have mobility choices (mobility poverty). A similar approach was taken from the Copenhagen pilot, identifying an underrepresented group of inhabitants with international backgrounds living in Ørestad. For Borghi, age was the most relevant criterion because the young population is scarce in Gerace and the villages of the Turano Valley.

6 Situational onboarding

For the GREENGAGE Project, onboarding is an ongoing process in which target groups learn about the pilot and how they can actively participate. It implies engaging identified groups in a joint endeavour. Onboarding is not a single static phase or activity. We will use the term onboarding rather than recruitment as it better suits the co-creation and ethical approach that informs GREENGAGE's values and vision. The onboarding process occurs gradually by generating interest and diversifying participation options through continuous engagement initiatives.

With the onboarding, we want people to decide to participate in the Citizens Observatory activities, address barriers to participation and relate to the different possible participant motivations. Onboarding people from marginalised groups is a priority in line with the GREENGAGE Citizens Observatories' equity, diversity, and inclusion principles. To engage with people considering their situation, we introduced the idea of situational onboarding in the GREENGAGE Methodological Framework (Deliverable 2.1). Situational onboarding is sensitive to context, time, capacities, and other variables that impact the ability of citizens to participate actively in Citizen Observatories. It seeks to meet people where they are and extend participants' contributions at different stages of the co-creation process.

The GREENGAGE methodology suggested reflexive questions to prepare initiatives for different stages of the Citizen Observatory. They aimed to guarantee, among others, to a) identify target groups to be onboard because of their expected contribution and the impact they will experience from the outcomes of our Citizen Observatory, b) considered the ethical and practical implications of providing or not providing entry points to meaningful participation in the core group for specific target groups, c) be clear about the purpose of the first gatherings and identify forms that will help the CO achieve its purpose, d) identify safe, comfortable and efficient communication channels to interact, and e) identify the needed tools, materials, and technologies for the onboarding.

These subjects were developed as part of the CO Academy Roadmapping through the second consortium meeting, IAB and PST meetings, WP3 workshops and WP3 meetings with pilots. The following sections first describe each preparation activity to later explain the alignment of the GREENGAGE methodology to the pilots' updated situation and finally illustrate the preparation activities carried out as a consequence.

6.1 Onboarding preparation phase activities: CO Academy Roadmapping

The CO Academy Roadmap is "a strategic, structured step-by-step plan for each pilot that shows how we aim to demonstrate the new way of policy making through setting up COs & what we do to develop the GREENGAGE approach on COs at the Academy alongside" (GREENGAGE, Clear Up - How do we approach Co-creation).

In concrete terms, it aims in the preparation phase at a) Defining the starting points of each pilot owner based on screening questionnaires (including the vision and mission of the pilots, objectives, and stakeholders), b) Situating the Citizen Observatory in the pilot, showing the role of citizens and GREENGAGE technologies, c) Define ethics and collaboration rules to be committed to by all members, d) Define communication channels to be used by COs and the rest of the consortium, e) Define the tools and technologies that are planned to be used in each citizen observatories, and f) Define the pilots' process for co-creating COs based on use cases and thematic co-explorations.

The CO Academy Roadmapping was not conceived as a fixed irreversible structure but rather as a working progress definition of parameters for the piloting and campaigning phase. As such, it is correlated to the development of GREENGAGE's different tasks and builds on the pilots' local situation. The CO Academy Roadmap was developed along the following collaborative activities during the second semester of 2023:

6.1.1 Second Consortium Meeting

During the second consortium meeting in Vienna, Austria (17-19 October 2023), the CO Academy Roadmap was further developed in the pilot Support Teams session, the collective discussion on WP3, and a workshop session with all the partners.

Collective discussion on WP3

Having the situational analysis as a reference, a basic typology of Citizen Observatory actors was reiterated and agreed upon. Based on a large group of identified target audiences, the onboarding activities should help determine who could be part of a core team, a Citizen Observer group or a stakeholder.

By core team, we mean a group of members who enable and lead the Observatory. The core team provides more in-depth analysis and is involved in strategic direction. The composition and roles of the core team can vary depending on the specific goals and focus of a Citizens Observatory. Some possible functions of such a group are: a) Engaging and involving more community members in the CO, b) Helping to ensure that data collection, analysis, and reporting activities are organised and on track, c) Communicating observatory findings to citizens observers, policymakers, and other stakeholders, and d) Developing and implementing governance structures and guidelines for the observatory's operations and supporting general observatory operations and initiatives.

Other potential participants could be Citizen Observers, members primarily having a central role in specific data collection, monitoring, analysis, engaging, raising awareness, communication and being part of advocacy activities. Other target groups might be included as part of the CO as stakeholders: allies or partners of the Observatory that can enhance their reach or impact (e.g., local institutions).

CO Academy Roadmap Workshop

With all the consortium partners, the activation plan of the Noord Brabant pilot was fully developed and used as input for the upcoming onboarding activities. A workshop was organised following the Bristol Approach co-creation stages: identifying, framing, designing, testing, sharing and reflecting. In the workshop, questions on identifying and framing were used to foster the preparation process of onboarding the GREENGAGE COs. The thematic areas were:

- Defining our CO: Simplify the CO explanation with a clear message for target audiences (co-thematic explorations, research themes).
- Building your core group and stakeholder mapping: Thanks to the participants, identify additional stakeholders to enlarge the community and tasks and expectations of the core team.
- Activating the target groups: Identify who we need in the CO, how should we reach them, and their capacity to get engaged, and compliance to the EDI framework.
- Onboarding: Think about external (target groups) and internal (data collection and management procedures, dedicated engagement team) as part of the onboarding.

These subjects were developed as part of two activities:

1. A persona-building exercise in which each stakeholder relevant to the Noord Brabant pilot was developed to analyse the role, interests, and better stage to be involved in the onboarding activities. A persona form was filled out based on the key stakeholders identified in the activation plan.
2. A role-play approach was applied to the stakeholders' personas to create a stakeholder map in terms of the different roles that each actor involved in the CO may play: as part of the core team, the Citizen Observatory or as a stakeholder. The role play was intertwined with a collective discussion to feed the stakeholders' map, as depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Stakeholder analysis in the CO Academy Roadmap Workshop

6.1.2 CO Academy Workshops with Pilots

The CO Academy Roadmapping occurred through workshops between the social engagement partners, members of PSTs and the pilot owners. Building on the second meeting workshop, the objectives of the workshops were: i) Align onboarding material to specific pilot narratives and target groups, ii) Align training material to specific pilot narratives and target groups, iii) Agree with each pilot on an onboarding plan, and iv) Agree with each pilot on a roadmap for training.

The CO Academy Workshop was conducted virtually (Miro board, depicted in Figure 7) with Gerace, Turano and Noord Brabant pilots, and a hybrid (virtual and in-person) workshop was conducted with the Bristol pilot. The workshops had a two (2) to four (4)-hour duration. The expected outputs of the workshops were to start providing tailored materials, agree on timelines, prepare recruitment surveys, and run one onboarding session and training session. The agenda of the workshops covered the following topics:

- Review and agree on key concepts such as onboarding, registration, core group, and goals for the onboarding process.
- Present a working-in-progress onboarding training material and discuss the relevance of themes for training, such as (general approaches to citizen science, onboarding, and ethics) and what could be of interest based on the latest updates.
- Review the pilot specification to improve a draft presentation prepared by the program and see if it fits the onboarding plans.
- Fit the plan to onboard the identified marginalised groups and prepare specific onboarding activities in the future.
- The workshop outcomes were cleared up in a WP3 meeting and presented and discussed with the Innovation Action Board in November.

Figure 7. Screenshot from online CO Academy Roadmap Workshop

6.1.3 Onboarding and training update meetings

WP3 held an update online meeting with each pilot in the last week of November (28 and 29 November 2023). Each session lasted 30-45 minutes focusing on the following purposes:

- Update the pilot situation: Pilot owners bring their political, institutional, social, and operational situation up to date in the face of the incoming onboarding and training activities.
- Review onboarding plans and support needed: WP3 presented the landing page for registration of interest and check on ethical guidelines and surveys to be applied.
- Review of training themes and times: WP3 presented a draft of the training package and received comments from pilots.

6.1.4 Ethics considerations

The GREENGAGE ethical framework is defined by: a) the deliverable D1.9 GREENGAGE Ethical Management Plan and Activities 1; b) the deliverable D1.11 Data Management Plan 1 c) the commitment made to Ethics approval from the College of Art Technology and Environment Research Ethics Committee of the University of West of England, Bristol and d) the commitment made to Ethics committees of University of DEUSTO and Breda University of Applied Science (BUAS).

The GREENGAGE Ethics Board, a focal point for assistance on ethics-related issues, operationalises such a framework. The GREENGAGE Ethics Board comprises project partners and pilot owners with expertise in Social Sciences and Humanities and GREENGAGE technologies. Led by UWE researchers, designated representatives from each of the pilot owners, AIT, BUAS, and DEUSTO, have a sit on the board.

The following ethics tasks have been carried out concerning the preparation and activation of onboarding and training activities:

- Participant information sheets (PISs) for each pilot were drafted. The PIS provides comprehensive information regarding each pilot: a) general description, b) aims and objectives, c) voluntary participation, d) expected participation and related benefits, e) possible risks, f) information data privacy, g) intended use of results, h) contact information of local pilot and GREENGAGE project. The forms must be branded locally for each pilot and complemented with local relevant information (e.g., specific dates).

- Participant consent forms (PCFs) for each pilot were drafted. The PCF includes a checklist of the information provided on the PIS to be signed by interested participants. The forms must be branded locally for each pilot and must be completed with pertinent information regarding the withdrawal dates for data use.
- A Privacy Notice for Research Participants was drafted. The privacy notice explains how personal data is collected, managed and used before, during and after participating in the GREENGAGE project. Includes a) what data is collected and for what purpose, b) with whom it is shared, c) how it is kept secure and for how long, d) your rights under the Data Protection legislation, e) contact in case of complaint or queries.

The first training on ethics was carried out with pilot owners and other partners. A full description can be found in section 7 of this report.

6.2 Onboarding in the Activation Phase

The onboarding of Citizen Observers was planned as a soft onboarding following a two-phased process. In the first phase, individuals are encouraged to indicate their interest in pilot participation. In the second phase, they are formally invited to become a Citizen Observer and registered.

The soft onboarding approach responds to the update of pilot context and specific needs emerging from the activities reported in the situational onboarding chapter while encompassing GREENGAGE's general structure of activities and its methodological framework. Challenges identified during the preparation activities that required the flexibility of the onboarding strategy were:

Political and social uncertainty in Bristol Pilot: There was an unexpected need to provide temporary accommodation for most Barton House residents, a tower block located in the chosen geographical areas for the pilot (East Bristol). The municipality had focused all its efforts on responding to the social emergency, and continued surveying is being undertaken to assess the building's status. Until a significant change in the local context, no social and ethical conditions were met to start onboarding activities. Along the same lines, training activities could be directed only to pilot owners. Once social and ethical conditions for onboarding are met, information activities could be re-interpreted as a re-engagement in the context of the Liveable Neighbourhoods programme. Nonetheless, possible adaptive measures were under assessment as part of the intermediation activities between the pilot and the GREENGAGE consortium. At the beginning of the year 2024, the Bristol Administration approved the advertising of the Traffic Regulation Order (TRO) for the entire EBLN scheme (due to begin in late January). The mobilization of a first CO will then begin between January and March 2024.

Political uncertainty in Gerace: The sudden passing of Gerace's Mayor during the summer affected the town's population, which had a strong link with the local authorities and compelled a pause amidst the collective grieving. It also forced an adaptation in the planned activities, given the municipal authorities' central role as stakeholders. The political transition process is still in progress with the designation of an acting Mayor who was briefed about the GREENGAGE project and the synergies with other initiatives carried out by Borghi.

The value of technological tools in the onboarding phase: For Gerace and Turano Valley pilot owners, the complete description of the technologies used in the Citizen Observatories is crucial for a successful onboarding activity. The pilot owners have already presented the project to diverse potential stakeholders and identified the great curiosity that the GREENGAGE platform, sensors and other technologies bring to potential members of the CO. Finding the best suit of the technological offer of GREENGAGE to pilot vision emerged as crucial information for successful onboarding. Copenhagen pilot also expressed the relevance of an accurate fit between technological tools as a condition for democratic data validation, reliability and the effective use of specific opportunities for political incidence.

Timing Vs opportunity challenges: The practical implementation in Ørestad on urban life aimed to bring about a mutually acknowledged dataset as part of the democratic process of developing a local plan amid controversies between the municipal authorities and local citizens' organisations. The data

collection was highly dependent on timely activities before the Winter season as climate and social practices drastically alter the mobility and usability of public spaces and potential participants' engagement. The impossibility of starting data collection in the fall was coped by renewed opportunities for political incidence identified in the development of a new municipal plan for local traffic. Its original aim was, to promote democratic debate, through participatory data collection in conjunction with planning over a validated and recognised dataset. This process involves adjusting the situational analysis (e.g., understanding the regulatory framework on different administrative levels) and the mechanisms to provide complementary local knowledge to planning parameters. Similar considerations were made in the North Brabant pilot as the Citizens Observers' registration activities were deemed not ideal to be carried out at the end of the year. Information and indications of interest activities were carried out to re-engage with those interested after the Christmas and New Year holidays.

The updated situational analysis was also helpful in providing alignment to training activities: A training-for-trainers approach and a training package were defined to start training activities with pilot owners and possible existing so called "ambassadors" from the group of future Citizen Observers in the pilots. This package was designed from a training-for-trainers approach and merged general subjects deemed needed to start a CO (e.g., ethics) and other shared topics of interest (a complete account can be found in section 7). A common interest was how data can effectively be used and transformed into validated and actionable knowledge for fruitful political incidence and policymaking. Some pilots made specific requests regarding the emphasis on citizens' training and provide guidance on how to use, analyse, and interpret open data. In general terms, there was a claim for specific training activities in each technological solution chosen for its own goals and the need to be scheduled in due time in the context of their plan of activities during the piloting phase.

The GREENGAGE onboarding process for Citizen Observers was streamlined through the GREENGAGE website, which will function as a common entry point for CO participants, facilitating the registration of interest process. To enhance the pilot functionality of the GREENGAGE website, a Website Pilot Requirements and Clarifications Survey was disseminated to gather requirements and seek clarifications. This survey was designed to tailor the engagement strategy to the local context, ensuring that the platform meets the specific needs of its users. Pilots in Copenhagen, Bristol and North Brabant have also decided to keep their already well-known websites and tools as primary entry points for onboarding and registration but pointing their citizen further to the GREENGAGE website for the actual CO facilitation.

An investigation was conducted into the registration and Citizen Observer login workflow, focusing on anonymisation and metadata collection procedures during onboarding to uphold privacy and data integrity as well as compliance to ethics protocols. For those potential participants who are not e-literate, a paper registration will be set in place.

Simultaneously, a comprehensive and didactical version of the Citizen Observer Journey diagram for the webpage was designed to be displayed on the GREENGAGE website. The Citizen Observer, Pilot Owner and Citizen Observatory Journeys aim to provide complete and simplified information on the process entailing being a citizen observer in each pilot. These journeys present the vision that each city wants to achieve, the thematic areas covered, the technological tools of the GREENGAGE Engine available for each theme to be researched, and the steps that encompass for a participant (onboarding, training, participation in analysis and production of data to be used by citizens and other stakeholders).

The following section describes those activities carried out to inform and reveal the interest of potential participants (phase one of the soft onboarding approach).

6.2.1 North Brabant Pilot

BUAS Cycling Lab Lunch Session

The BUAS Cycling Lab is a collection of lunch sessions that aim to facilitate using the bike in daily life, in every way possible. Whether you would like to try to commute on a bike, get more skilled in fixing bike problems, or understand why you like biking, these sessions address the obstacles and motivations of bike use and provide solutions or enhancements. A lunch session is a physical interactive meeting in

which, through a brief presentation of scenarios, different obstacles and motivators to biking are discussed and later quantified through a survey.

This first meeting was an introductory event, after which participants could decide whether to continue or not. From the North Brabant pilot perspective, the cycling lab is considered as a pre-pilot. Before setting up localised citizen observatories that gather data, these university-focused sessions give a preliminary insight into the decision-making process around using bikes for journeys. This insight into decision-making (through an updated theory of planned behaviour) will be instrumental in shaping future citizen observatories when specific use cases can be discussed in more detail.

The purpose of this first meeting was threefold:

- Engage voluntary participants to join in for more sessions.
- Identify participants' biking proficiency.
- Gather survey data on participants' travel patterns and bike motivators/obstacles.

The event was carried out on 5 December 2023 from 12:00-13:00 (CET). As a lunch meeting, participants were provided a simple lunch as well. The event took place at the Breda University of Applied Science campus, Frontier building, room Fs2.004.

To invite participants for this introductory event, the Breda University of Applied Science website portal was used to reach all university staff from 7 different academies. The event details were published one month in advance through the website portal. In addition, all staff of all BUAS academies were contacted through an internal BUAS email server. Verbal invitations were also used through personal connections in BUAS academies. In total, about 700 people were contacted.

The event was held in English and the invitation to participation was open to everyone regardless of gender, age or background. To ensure marginalised group participation, the anglophonic focus targeted international staff members who would like to increase their familiarity with biking, a more prominent feature of non-Dutch participants. While not explicitly demarcated as an Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) activity, one of the main points of the Cycling Lab is to inventory, understand, and respectfully discuss diverse reactions to cycling. EDI was followed by keeping an open discussion and pursuing means to strive for personal biking goals – whatever they may be.

The event attracted 20 people (as depicted in Figure 8 and Figure 9), with about 30 more indicating interest but claiming a conflicting schedule. Of those participating, 75% had a Dutch background, and 25% had an international one (Russia, Iran, Indonesia, and the United Kingdom). 60% of the attendees were female, while 40% were male. About 40% had a background in mobility, whereas 60% came from tourism, leisure, or design backgrounds. All were highly educated, lived in or around Breda, and had some knowledge of biking.

The event consisted of several steps:

1. Introduction to REENGAGE and the Cycling Lab goals
2. Introduction of participants, focusing on a) Their name b) Their city of residence c) Their average biking behaviour during a week
3. A quickfire presentation of obstacles and motivators, with thumb up/down gauging whether the scenarios would dissuade participants from biking. The aim here was to identify preliminary differences and familiarise participants with possible obstacles/motivators.
4. A scheduled bit of time in which they could physically fill in a questionnaire about their travel habits, obstacles/motivators for biking, and what they would want to get out of future sessions. An information letter and a consent form were provided. The participants were told that their surveyed data would be used to expand the theory of planned behaviour and to plan future sessions.

During the event, it was made clear that the goal was not to get everyone on a bike but to identify why the bike does not work in daily travel and whether there are small actions that can enable biking. As

such, the session was focused on discussing anecdotes, scientifically identified obstacles and motivators, and creating an inventory of specific worries. Cultural or personal differences in opinion or perspectives were discussed in detail to understand the different interpretations of biking. Everyone's opinion in this sense was valid, as the focus was entirely on comprehending the decision-making process, not influencing it. Everyone's background was voluntarily discussed (in the context of biking) and their motivations or barriers. To ensure everyone is valued, participants were invited to share their own goals and objections so that they could be addressed in future sessions.

Participants were told that future sessions would deal with the specific obstacles they want to address (like bringing in a mechanic if a bike breaking down is experienced as a problem). From this call, specific and culturally unique topics were brought forward (like a lack of information on Dutch cycling rules for expats or judgmental behaviour by the Dutch to cultural objections to biking).

Contrary to expectations, the event primarily attracted people with a high bike proficiency. While there were bikers from underrepresented groups (people with no cultural affinity to biking), it was lower than expected. The implications could be seen in the questionnaire responses and desired future actions, for example, the responses focused more on bike use optimisation (e.g., how can electric bikes be integrated decisively into the mobility policy) or experiments on commuting by bike (lessons learned from avid bikers), and not on basic biking skills.

Figure 8. GREENGAGE project presentation at BUAs Cycling Lab Lunch Session

Figure 9. Participants at GREENGAGE's presentation at BUAs Cycling Lab Lunch Session

At the end of the session 18 of the 20 participants indicated their intention to continue with the cycling lab. The promise of addressing their obstacles in future sessions motivated them enough to express that they would join again. The participants were more interested in solving their problems and diving more explicitly into the decision-making process than in gathering related quantitative data. While the session worked well as a format to bring together a group of citizens to reflect and expand on a theoretical model (a form of self-observatory), made evident the challenge of motivating participants within a Citizen Observatory aiming to gather quantitative data.

6.2.2 Gerace and Turano Valley Pilot

The Gerace and Turano Valley presented the GREENGAGE project in the following different venues and to diverse potential participants and stakeholders in search of raising interest to participate.

Participation in the public meeting “Create opportunities for the relaunch of artisanal, productive and commercial activities operating in the territories of the municipalities benefiting from National Recovery and Resilience Plan funding (PNRR).” (Turano Valley)

This event showcased opportunities for relaunching activities of artisanal, productive and commercial companies operating in the territories of the municipalities benefiting from PNRR funding. The GREENGAGE project was presented in such a context as an opportunity to a) create synergies and improve policies relating to mobility through the specific approach of citizen observatories, b) raise awareness of climate and environmental issues, and c) promote sustainable urban policies supported through evidence extracted from data.

The main objective of the intervention within the meetings was to raise awareness among the participants about the GREENGAGE project, spreading information regarding the upcoming construction of a Citizen Observatory. The meeting focused on the importance of involving the community and authorities in building sustainable solutions to address the challenges related to climate change.

The public meeting was held on 9 June 2023 at the Multifunctional Hall of Castel di Tora Municipality, Largo Massimi (as depicted in Figure 10 and Figure 11). It lasted for an hour and a half. In total, 70 people attended, including citizens, entrepreneurs, non-profit organisations, representatives of public and private institutions, and universities. The meeting had an equal participation of men and women. Following the Municipality’s and GREENGAGE’s attention to EDI, the meeting created an environment where all voices could be heard equally and safely.

The response from participants during and after the event was positive. The presentation of the GREENGAGE project resonated well with the audience, and participants viewed it as a valuable opportunity to foster collaboration and synergies. There was a noticeable interest in the potential for the project to enhance policies related to mobility, with participants recognising the importance of incorporating citizen perspectives through the proposed Citizen Observatory. The attendees were curious about using technological tools that can facilitate understanding of environmental and climate-related problems and values. The prospect of leveraging data through a Citizen Observatory was particularly appealing, as it was seen as a powerful tool to inform and support sustainable urban policies.

Figure 10. Invitation to Public Meeting in Turano Valley

Figure 11. Participants in Public Meeting in Turano Valley

Participation in Borghi Uniti per la rigenerazione culturale e sociale della Valle del Turano” (“Villages united for the cultural and social regeneration of the Turano Valley

The pilot participated in the Hybrid meeting “*Borghi Uniti per la rigenerazione culturale e sociale della Valle del Turano*” (“*Villages united for the cultural and social regeneration of the Turano Valley*”), a project financed by the European Union – Next Generation EU, an initiative seeking the valorisation of the entire Valley of Turano (municipalities of Collalto Sabino, Castel di Tora and Paganico Sabino). The meeting was held at the Municipality of Collalto Sabino on 12 August 2023 from 16:30 to 18:30 (CET).

As depicted in Figure 12 and Figure 13, the participation aimed to raise awareness and foster interest in the GREENGAGE project by spreading information on the future creation of a Citizen Observatory to

promote innovative governance processes and help public authorities define their climate mitigation and adaptation policies.

The municipalities of Collalto Sabino, Castel di Tora and Paganico Sabino invited their population through a public notice. The meeting was also advertised by spreading the word. The call sought to allow a broader audience to participate and increase accessibility. The organisers worked actively to ensure that all people, regardless of gender or mode of participation, felt represented and included. In this way, the event sought to respect the principles of equity, diversity and inclusion, creating a welcoming experience for all participants.

Seventy people attended the meeting (49 in-person and 21 online), including citizens, entrepreneurs, non-profit organisations and representatives of public and private institutions, including universities. The participation between men and women was even.

At the end of the event, a total of 54 (34 participants in-person and 20 online) declared interest in continuing participation in GREENGAGE CO activities. Participants perceived that the project could help protect the area in which they live, which has a high and particular natural value, by paying attention to the need for sustainable, cultural and inclusive growth necessary for the area.

Figure 12. Public Presentation of GREENGAGE in the context of the event "Borghi uniti per la rigenerazione culturale e sociale della Valle di Turano"

Figure 13. Borghi presentation of GREENGAGE in the context of the event "Borghi uniti per la rigenerazione culturale e sociale della Valle di Turano"

Coordination meetings with representatives of the Municipality of Gerace

The pilot held two technical coordination meetings with the participation of representatives of the Association “The Most Beautiful Villages in Italy” and representatives of the Municipality of Gerace. The meetings were run at the Municipality of Gerace on the 29 and 30 of August 2023 and lasted between two and three hours each. Five representatives of the Municipality of Gerace, including the acting Mayor, and four representatives of the Borghi (Association “The Most Beautiful Villages of Italy”) attended the meeting.

The meeting’s goal was to present the project to key stakeholders. As depicted in Figure 14 and Figure 15, the presentation included the goal and aims of GREENGAGE, a Citizens' Observatory strategy, the possible synergies with other initiatives in the pilot - like “Porta del Sole”- and the governance model and role of the Citizen Observatory on it.

The meeting in Gerace served as a pivotal moment for stakeholders to gain a comprehensive understanding of the project's objectives and potential impacts on the local community. The active participation of local authorities and experts from the Borghi generated a constructive dialogue, paving the way for better collaboration in the GREENGAGE field and the implementation of concrete actions for the promotion of sustainable and innovative policies thanks to the support of the Citizen Observatory.

The responses from participants at the Municipality of Gerace during and after the meeting were highly positive and indicated strong interest in the GREENGAGE project. The municipality representatives have shown interest in collaborating with the project. Particular attention was expressed towards the possible synergies with the "Porta del Sole" project planned in Gerace and how GREENGAGE can be applied. The potential for GREENGAGE to bring added value to the Do Not Significantly Harm (DSNH) principle envisioned for projects financed with National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) funds was widely acknowledged. The meetings found significant potential for alignment of GREENGAGE with broader regional development goals and the aspiration to contribute meaningfully to the PNRR. The representatives of the Municipality of Gerace demonstrated a keen interest in the study of local mobility data. They acknowledged the importance of informed decision-making in policymaking and the relevance of environmental and climatic themes on local agenda. They also appreciated the holistic approach emerging from the project's objectives. Expectations were notably high, and participants were enthusiastic about implementing concrete actions that promote sustainable and innovative policies, mainly through the Citizen Observatory.

The administration indicated a list of possible relevant local stakeholders and how, based on the technologies and training program details, the most suitable stakeholders to benefit from these services/activities can be better specified.

After the meeting, an entry was published on the official website of the Borghi piu Belli di Italia (news section) See: <https://borghipiubelliditalia.it/2023/09/29/i-borghi-piu-belli-ditalia-partecipano-al-progetto-GREENGAGE/>. It describes the goals, approach, and GREENGAGE partners thoroughly and provides a link to the GREENGAGE webpage.

The invitation was sent to 50 participants through the communication channels and spreading the word within the Order. 38 people attended the meeting, 16 women and 22 men.

As depicted in Figure 16 and Figure 17, the objective of the presentation was to raise architects' awareness of the GREENGAGE initiative in synergy with the local regeneration project called "Villages United for the Cultural and Social Regeneration of the Turano Valley" (Funded by Next Generation EU). GREENGAGE was framed as a project part of the "Process of Regeneration of the Villages of Turano".

GREENGAGE's aims, objectives, approach, and different pilots were described during the presentation. Also, the available platforms and technological support planned for the Gerace and Turano Valley pilot were explained to the audience: a) sensors and applications for the data collection, b) the Collaborative Environment for experimenting on citizen science, and c) data analysis tools. A contact mail was offered for those interested in the project.

The project called the attention and interest of the architects about the participatory process activity planned through the Citizen Observatory and Borghi più belli d'Italia. As a result of the activity, the Order and Borghi più Belli d'Italia opened a channel to keep the Order of Architects of Rieti informed about future GREENGAGE activities, events and steps.

GREENGAGE
ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL
(www.greengage-project.eu)

Borghi più belli d'Italia

Gli interessati a prendere parte al progetto, possono manifestare l'interesse scrivendo a:
project@borhipiubelliditalia.it

Abstract del progetto

GREENGAGE è un'azione di innovazione paneuropea della durata di 3 anni (gennaio 2023 - dicembre 2025) finanziata nell'ambito del programma quadro Horizon Europe. Il consorzio, guidato dall'Istituto Austriaco di Tecnologia, è composto da 17 partner dell'UE e del Regno Unito.

GREENGAGE promuove processi di governance innovativi e aiuta le autorità pubbliche a definire le proprie politiche di mitigazione e adattamento climatico. Per raggiungere questo obiettivo, il progetto GREENGAGE opera per favorire la partecipazione dei cittadini tramite l'organizzazione di Osservatori Cittadini e fornisce soluzioni digitali innovative, fornendo così le basi per co-creare e co-progettare soluzioni per il monitoraggio dei problemi ambientali. Gli Osservatori Cittadini saranno ulteriormente incorporati nel processo decisionale di pianificazione urbana per co-creare iniziative sostenibili concentrandosi su mobilità, qualità dell'aria e vita sana a sostegno della creazione di quartieri a emissioni zero, in linea con gli obiettivi del Green Deal europeo.

L'azione di innovazione sull'opera un processo di governance innovativo implementando soluzioni digitali integrate con osservazione satellitare della Terra (servizi Copernicus) e dati in situ per trasformare l'impegno dei cittadini a favore del potenziamento della governance locale e per favorire opportunità sociali e culturali.

Concentrandosi sulla mobilità, sulla qualità dell'aria e sulla vita sana, i cittadini, nell'ambito di appositi Osservatori Cittadini, potranno reperire, convalidare, arricchire informazioni esistenti in dati autorevoli. Tali informazioni basate sull'evidenza saranno utilizzate a supporto dei processi decisionali delle politiche locali e per una governance urbana intelligente.

Le attività previste saranno realizzate in quattro aree pilota in città e regioni europee selezionate, tra cui: Bristol (Regno Unito), Copenhagen (Danimarca), Turano - Gerace (Italia) e la regione del Brabant Settentrionale (Paesi Bassi). Questi casi d'uso mirano a evidenziare la necessità di una governance per le città intelligenti promuovendo il coinvolgimento dei cittadini, attraverso processi di co-creazione, raccolta di nuovi dati che integreranno i set di dati esistenti e il processo decisionale e politico basato sull'evidenza.

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Figure 16. GREENGAGE presentation in Event of Order of Architects of Rieti, Turano Valley

Figure 17. Presentation of the GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory in Turano Valley, event of Order of Architects of Rieti, Turano Valley

Public Event ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP FOR THE REGENERATION OF GERACE - Opportunities offered by the GREENGAGE and Gerace, PORTA DEL SOLE projects”

The public event was organised by “Borghi più belli d’Italia” (The Most Beautiful Villages in Italy) in collaboration with the Municipality of Gerace. It aimed to present to citizens and potential GREENGAGE stakeholders the opportunities offered by the "Gerace, Porta del Sole" and GREENGAGE projects and their synergies for active citizenship and the regeneration of the territory.

The specific objectives of the meeting were: i) present the GREENGAGE project and highlight the opportunity for "active citizenship" in Gerace ii) explain the synergies between the GREENGAGE and “Gerace Porta del Sole” "(Gerace, Gate of the Sun)" project and the related agreements with the Municipality of Gerace, iii) start inviting citizens and all stakeholders to express their interest in the future GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory to support data-based decisions and active citizenship. An online form to register for the event and to express interest in the project was set up, too: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/GREENGAGE-in-Gerace>

The event took place on the 21 December 2023 at the Council Room of the Municipality of Gerace (Italy), Piazza del Tocco, 3, 17:30 – 19:00 (CET).

Invitations were sent to identified main GREENGAGE stakeholders (citizens, policymakers, non-profit associations and local companies, schools, higher education institutions and local media) via email from the Municipality of Gerace and from “The Most Beautiful Villages in Italy”. The public meeting was also posted on social media channels. Gender balance was considered when preparing the invitations and through the list of non-profit associations, particular attention was given to a more general inclusion of vulnerable groups.

7 Training

7.1 Training program

The training activities of GREENGAGE are organised in two stages.

Stage I comprises the Train-the-Trainers program, a series of weekly webinars taking place from December 2023 until March 2024. The first nine sessions cover the following themes: (1) ethics, (2) data management and (3) visualisation, (4) citizen science and observatories, (5) co-design methodologies and tools, (6) policymaking and governance, as well as (7-9) overview of and guidance for GREEN Engine technologies with focus on tools and apps for mobility, infrastructure, and environmental monitoring (see table below for more details).

No	Theme	Focus	W/C
1	Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public Ethics Awareness /Contact of care - GREENGAGE Privacy Notice - Participation Information Sheets - Personal Consent Forms - FAQs ethics for pilot owners & CObs 	04-Dec-23
2	Data I	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General intro to data science & management - Intro on reliance on AI, Machine learning, and Intelligence involved in the data-mining cycle - Data governance and standards - Scientific methods for data collection and sampling - Data management applied to the technologies - Tools for data harmonisation, workflow management and analysis - Possibilities & challenges of qualitative data-driven storytelling 	15-Jan-24
3	Data II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dealing with types of data (earth, sensing, authoritative data sets) - Open data (Accessing geospatial info from OpenStreetMap and Copernicus data) - Explanation of Copernicus tools & services (data management and use) - Data quality and visualisation, analysis and validation - Data and benefits for citizens, municipalities and stakeholders - Data protocol and workflow configuration - Explanation of location-based mobility data 	22-Jan-24
4	Co-design I	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General principles of scientific work - Citizen Science (CS) - Citizen Observatories (How to co-design a contract of care/guiding principles together with CObs) - Overview of participatory methods & tools (analogue & digital) - Co-producing Citizen Observatories (whole process management from co-design to co-delivery) - Roadmapping CS activities & processes for policy innovation - Strategies to sustain motivation - Asset Based Community Development (ABCD) 	29-Jan-24
5	Co-design II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussion on how to co-create a use case (environmental, mobility, infrastructure) and its monitoring - overview of actual on-ground possibilities for carrying out thematic co-explorations in pilots - Tools for community dialogue and collaborative process management - Lessons learned from other EU CS projects (WeObserve, Decido,..) 	05-Feb-24

6	Policy-making & Governance	- Policy making per thematic co-exploration - Urban planning & governance - Sharing experience from the field - Mechanisms and support to transit from data evidence to policymaking	12-Feb-24
7	Technology I	- Intro to GREEN Engine (REENGAGE tools and methods) - Demo of technologies & how to use them (including AI component and ethics involved): 1. Social Coin (DEUSTO) 2. Collaborative Environment (DEUSTO) 3. Data Space Enabling Technology (DEUSTO) 4. DigiTwin (BUAS) 5. ATMOTUBE PRO & NOISOTUBE Analysis	19-Feb-24
8	Technology II	- Demo of technologies & how to use them: 6. Image Analysis & Realtime Mapping (MindEarth) 7. Movesense (Moondial) 8. MODE (AIT) 9. AUDABLOK (DEUSTO)	26-Feb-24
9	Technology III	- Demo of technologies & how to use them: 10. Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVIS) 11. UTEP / VISAT (GISAT) 12. REENGAGE app (SUSHIDEV)	04-Mar-24
10	TBD by pilots' needs	- contextual discussion on pilots incl. challenges (peer-to-peer learning)	TBD
11	TBD Lessons learned	- Sharing stories, experiences from each pilot - Listening to the voices and feedback of observers and trainers	TBD

Two more sessions will be planned at the end of the nine sessions. These will be shaped and organised by pilot owners allowing for peer-to-peer learning whilst sharing contextual challenges and lessons learned from each pilot. Furthermore, topics which were not addressed previously will now be tackled, best corresponding to the evolving project and pilots' needs.

Each of the formal training sessions will be accompanied by a follow-up informal meeting focusing on the practical implementation of the training material by pilot trainers. Hands-on questions and step-by-step practical guidance will be provided then.

The scope of Stage I, including both formal and informal sessions, is to confidently equip the pilot owners and ambassadors with essential skills on how-to-run-a-Citizen-Observatory and provide them with useful in-depth knowledge on different topics as these were identified from the situational onboarding in preparation for Stage II.

Stage II of the training activities will then be concerned with the onboarding and training of Citizen Observers (CObs) and will start shortly after the recruitment of the local teams has been completed. Currently, we are having detailed discussions and meetings regarding the planning of this stage and how it may align with the piloting and campaigning of CObs (WP5), addressing issues of time commitment, language barriers, impact assessment, personal CO journey options, sampling technique, and levels and dimensions of digital literacy.

7.2 Training preparation & material

To gauge interest and expertise within the consortium, an Expression of Interest questionnaire for REENGAGE Training was disseminated. The survey asked for, on the one hand, feedback from

partners and pilot owners on the suggested training themes and on the other hand, their expressed interest in developing content and/or delivering training around those themes.

The survey received several responses, and suggestions were integrated into the planning of the training. Based on the information gathered, we were able to recognize the need to set up working groups with different partners (educational & citizen-focused) and take advantage of the capacity of universities, for example, to curate and develop learning material and play a pivotal role in the delivery of the trainings. Another outcome from the survey and ongoing discussions was to reach out to external experts from other EU-funded related projects, like the DECIDO project coordinator, and invite them to share their experience in support for pilots and effective policymaking based on evidence and citizen contributions.

7.2.1 Knowledge Base

To organise the communication and dissemination of the training material, it was decided that the GREENGAGE website will undergo major restructuring and repurposing to, amongst others:

- serve as the entry point for the facilitation of the CO participants' registration
- publish a calendar of events for each pilot, announcing important dates and community activities
- host a library — Knowledge Base section on the GREENGAGE website — that will include recordings from the training sessions, short videos, references, and documentation for GREEN Engine technologies, and support material for the CO Academy. This will serve as the main point of reference for the Stage II of the training and an archive of relevant resources that both the public authorities and the citizens will be able to visit at their own time even after the end of the project.

In this sense and besides these, the Knowledge Base will also host the GREENGAGE project deliverables, publications and multimedia outputs. These changes will be gradually implemented under WP7, starting at the end of year 2023 / early January 2024.

7.3 Training activities

7.3.1 First GREENGAGE Training: Ethics in Citizen Observatories

Dr. Amanda Ramsay of UWE Bristol delivered the first training session on Ethics on 7 December 2023 (11:30-12:30 (CET)). Invitations were sent to all partners via e-mail with a follow-up reminder during the monthly GREENGAGE General Assembly Meeting. 23 people attended the session from different partners of the consortium.

The agenda of the session was the following:

- 10' Intro: brief description of training session package and scope of the first session
- 30' Presentation (in ppt format) by Amanda Ramsay. The presentation addressed key ethical issues that need to be considered when coordinating a CO or whilst conveying ethics information to potential COs. The topics reviewed were:
 - a. GREENGAGE's Ethic framework and commitments
 - b. GREENGAGE Ethics Board (composition, role and contact)
 - c. Basic principles of good ethical research
 - d. Equalities, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) principles
 - e. GREENGAGE Contract of Care
 - f. GREENGAGE Ethics Starter Kit, containing important documents for COs:

- i. Personal consent form (PCF)
 - ii. Participant information sheet (PIS)
 - iii. Privacy notice for Research Participants
 - iv. FAQs in ethics for both CObs and Pilot Owners
 - v. Links to access further GREENGAGE's ethics and data management documents
- 30' Questions and answers

A week later, the presentation slides, video recording of the session, and materials from the ethics training were distributed to all partners via e-mail. A feedback survey was also administered to ask for further input and suggestions from the consortium and ascertain the relevance of the activity to improve its delivery and make changes to future sessions.

Although this survey is still ongoing, a couple of points have already been noted:

Firstly, training can be more anchored to GREENGAGE pilots, including practical and contextualised examples. As one pilot owner mentioned: "I would have preferred that the training format was based precisely on the specific pilots", whilst a second one said: "While relevant, it remained detached from GREENGAGE. Perhaps try to link it to a pilot - which also allows for interaction to make the pilot think for themselves" and added "some more interaction, or positioning in the GREENGAGE context could help to make it more identifiable."

Secondly, timings and Q&A section at the end of the presentation worked very well. Specifically, it was pointed out that "30 minutes is a good time for concentrated training and the final part with Q&A is equally useful."

For us, the main lesson learned from this first session was how can we translate abstract theoretical training into practical actions and transferrable knowledge and how can we involve / support the pilot Support Teams to convey this knowledge in practical terms.

8 Conclusions

This report outlined the harmonisation of the GREENGAGE COs Methodological Framework with the unique characteristics of pilot cities and the planning and implementation of recruitment and training activities. It delves into GREENGAGE's strategies for addressing the distinctive aspects of each pilot city, tailoring solutions to suit their specific contexts while aiming for replicable results. Following the GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework, the report emphasised the project's active intermediation during the preparation phase and the establishment of a foundation for the upcoming piloting phase.

The GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework was designed to be a flexible and adaptable set of principles and processes to suit local situations while keeping a common path to achieve GREENGAGE objectives. This process was conceptualised as active intermediation. The primary alignments of the methodology during the intermediation processes were:

a) Organisational structures, processes, and tools to adapt to evolving situations in the pilots were established and introduced innovation to urban policymaking through digital engagement with citizens. The most relevant decisions in this sense have been to set up an organisational structure of different levels through the Innovation Action Board (IAB) and Pilot Support Teams (PSTs). The process involved drafting and testing an information flow through the set-up instances. It also made necessary, the Collaborative Environment's alignment to the CO Methodological Framework logic inspired by the Bristol Approach and the streamlined Citizen Observers Journey and Pilot Owner Journey.

b) A comprehensive understanding of relevant contextual information for each pilot through situational analysis was developed. The situational analysis was developed as a conceptual and methodological source for actively intermediate between the top-down and bottom-up trajectories: the GREENGAGE's objectives and possibilities and the pilot owners' situational needs. The outcome was a GREENGAGE roadmap outlining the steps for implementing CO initiatives in each city.

d) The conceptualisation and operationalisation of recruitment and training as situational onboarding in preparation for the piloting phase was carried out. A soft onboarding process of two phases (indication of interest and registration in the Citizen Observatory) was designed to adapt to GREENGAGE's updated situational analysis. In coherence, an initial training package formulated from a training and trainees' perspective was defined to reassure common knowledge of GREENGAGE's ethics commitments, collaborative approaches and technological possibilities between partners and pilot owners and guarantee confidence to begin training for members of the COs.

Further enhancements of the GREENGAGE CO Methodological framework and the organisational structure (IAB-PTs) could be expected in line with the pilots' situations, challenges, and possibilities during the piloting phase. The bottom-up flow of information during these phases will create opportunities to gather insights for the GREENGAGE Innovation Action and for the collaborative set-up of Citizen Observatories as Living Labs. In this sense, further links between the Collaborative Environment, the Innovation Action and the CO activation phase are expected. The deliverable D.3.3 CO Academy Roadmap contains a nuanced reflection on this matter.

Situational onboarding intends to capture the constant process of engaging with potential members of the CO considering the dynamic process of collaborative research. Further tailoring of onboarding activities is expected to be developed under WP5, and specific target groups and the needed specific training activities are based on the up-to-date roadmaps of each pilot city adapted to technological choices, target groups and local situations.

ANNEX A-GREENGAGE Conceptualising Stage - Situational screening of the pilots

1. Mission and Vision of this questionnaire

The questionnaire presented in this document is framed within the **conceptualisation phase** of a CO. This phase defines the initial steps necessary to launch a GREENGAGE CO. These steps comprise: (a) the (preliminary) top-down definition of the objectives of the CO, (b) the analysis of the current situation of the pilot owner in relation to all aspects and/or dimensions that are relevant for the launch and subsequent operation of the CO, and (c) the creation (mapping, engaging and gathering) of the first community of citizens that will participate in the CO, or Citizen Observers. At this point, the pilot owner would be ready to move on to the preparation phase. It should be noted that the CO stages are flexible and iterative, adapting to the specificities of each pilot and revising each stage whenever necessary.

The questionnaire pursues a double objective:

- 1) **Support the performance of a situational screening of the innovation pilots**, to be undertaken by the pilot owners, enquiring into the current context in the key dimensions that are relevant for setting-up and executing COs, namely (1) goals and objectives; (2) political, institutional and power dynamics; (3) technological; (4) public engagement; and (5) sociodemographic dimensions. The questions provided are a support tool to promote self-reflection and understanding of each innovation pilot's current situation.
- 2) **Perform situational analyses to define a strategy for the pilot owners to make the necessary adaptations to move forward in the CO conceptualisation stage.** The questionnaire will generate important information for the CO Coordinators to design appropriate tools, tech & practices in support of the pilot owners and in respect to the metrics of a co-designed IA. The coordinator's role in this stage of the GREENGAGE IA is to tailor the preparation of strategies & tools that enable the creation of GREENGAGE COs in the five pilots and to ensure that collective learning across the pilots is systematic in the way that it is looking for commonalities and differences across the pilots. The mentioned strategy will be co-defined between the pilot action groups - multidisciplinary teams of GREENGAGE partners covering all the required expertise to support a smooth execution of the CO activities - and the pilot owners. The strategy will provide insights addressing all the CO relevant dimensions, and once agreed and implemented, will allow pilot owners to move into the last stage of the CO conceptualisation stage – the situational onboarding of citizens or involvement of the first community of Citizen Observers.

In a few words, the questionnaire provided in this document will guide an information gathering process about the innovation pilots required to adapt the pilot owners' current situation in organisational, engagement, technological and communication terms in order to become prepared to start creating the first community of Citizen Observers. Furthermore, it also represents a general tool that can be applied to different situations for replicating the learnings of the GREENGAGE IA. Filling out this questionnaire will enable the pilots to understand better the relationships and aspects that matter in their specific situation.

The questionnaire is inspired by several sources of information, including D2.1 GREENGAGE COs Methodological Framework; D2.2 Use cases and requirement analysis I; D2.4 Smart Governance Models 1; brainstorming outcomes from several consortium meetings and the CPI Framework²

² M. Gharesifard, U. When and P. van der Zaag (2019). What influences the establishment and functioning of community-based monitoring initiatives of water and environment? A conceptual framework. *Journal of Hydrology* 579 (2019) 124033

developed in the frame of the GROUNDTRUTH project. The Community Based Initiatives (CPI) framework’s purpose is to analyse the dynamics underlying the establishment and functioning of “community-based initiatives” (similar to COs) by gathering information of context-related factors through different questions. It is suitable for “Situational analysis”, “Process evaluation” and “Impact assessment” of the initiatives.

1.1 What has been done up to this point? (within the conceptualising stage of the GREENGAGE COs)

To contextualise the questionnaire presented in this document, a description of the work performed in the GREENGAGE IA, related to the specifics of the conceptualising stage, until this point, is provided in the following lines:

- **GREENGAGE COs Methodological Framework** (included in the D2.1), which suggests core concepts, processes and guidelines on how to develop COs in GREENGAGE in ways that are ethical, democratic and responsive to common urban challenges and their situational manifestations in five pilots. It is the conceptual framework that provides a collective understanding of the key elements that have to be considered for the GREENGAGE purposes and objectives.
- **Use cases and requirements analysis v1** (included in the D2.2), a report introducing the innovation pilots and associated use cases and user requirements with the objective to highlight ‘What’ is expected. Different use cases and requirements were derived from the pilot specifications, and these will be implemented within the GREENGAGE IA.
- **Smart Governance models v1** (included in D2.4), provides the basis for GREENGAGE partners in the development of an urban governance model that incorporates and deploys the full potentials of COs in support of bottom-up engagement in urban planning decision-making.

1.2 Methodology - How to answer this questionnaire?

The situational screening questionnaire addresses five dimensions, namely (1) goals and objectives of the innovation pilots; (2) political, institutional and power dynamics; (3) technological; (4) public engagement; and (5) sociodemographic.

Pilot owners are responsible for answering the questions of the mentioned dimensions. Consultation of the different experts within the pilot owners’ organisation is encouraged. Additionally, each pilot owner should rely on the pilot action group for further clarification and support for the process of answering the questionnaire. Most of the questions follow a qualitative methodology, except for the sociodemographic analysis that is mainly based on quantitative indicators. The pilot owners in charge of answering these questions should be aware of the needs and objectives pursued for their specific CO.

In a second step, the key information delivered by the pilot owners through responding to the questionnaire will be properly processed and digested by the CO Coordinators, with the support of the pilot action groups, who will communicate a strategy composed of series of suggested activities that support the pilot owners to make the necessary adjustments and preparations with regards to the analysed dimensions to move forward in the conceptualisation stage of the CO.

2. Situational screening questionnaire

2.1 Goals and objectives of the innovation pilots

GREENGAGE innovation pilots’ overarching goals and objectives have been pre-defined by pilot owners. Having these objectives been defined by following a top-down approach, it is important to realise the different stakeholders that will be involved as Citizen Observers may have divergent interests or values and the objectives of the CO may incline more towards preferences and wishes of some stakeholders than those of others. The same can happen with the benefits these stakeholders can perceive.

Additionally, the innovation pilot goals and objectives were influenced by the European Green Deal, being the ultimate aim to contribute to the fulfilment of its targets through the means of establishing and functioning of the COs. However, the immediate impact of the GREENGAGE IA COs will be on those policies and plans in which the pilot owners have direct authority or influence capacity.

For those reasons, the following questions are focused on facilitating the self-assessment with regards to the connection of the Citizen Observers with the objectives of the innovation pilot.

To address the mentioned issues, the following questions should be considered:

1. Which stakeholders were consulted for the formulation of the objectives and goals of the CO? And why?
a. Public Institutions
b. Academia or groups of experts
c. Private enterprises
d. NGOs or other third sector groups
e. Citizens

Q1 Recommendation

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<p>2. Who are the potential beneficiaries of the defined CO goals? Please explain what the expected benefits per target group are.</p>
<p>a. Public Institutions</p>
<p>b. Academia or groups of experts</p>
<p>c. Private enterprises</p>
<p>d. NGOs or other third sector groups</p>
<p>e. Citizens</p>

<p>Q2 Recommendation:</p>

3. Please identify, according to the specific objectives of your innovation pilot, the national, regional and/or local policies and plans and their targets, that ultimately could be influenced by the results of the CO.

[Prompt] Related to your innovation pilot purposes. For example, Bristol aims at reducing air pollution, so they should identify the policy that sets the reduction target. This, in a later stage, will allow us to design the activities to be performed by the CO, in order to contribute to the target defined by the identified policy.

Q3 Recommendation

2.2 Political, institutional and power dynamics dimension

In the situational analysis of a CO, the political, institutional and power dynamics dimension holds significant importance. It refers to the recognition of and consideration of the political and institutional structures and processes that influence the functioning and impact of the CO.

The **political dimension** encompasses the policies and decision-making frameworks within which the CO operates. It involves understanding the relationships between different stakeholders, such as government bodies, regulatory authorities, and civil society organisations, and how these interactions shape the CO’s objectives, goals, and outcomes.

The **institutional dimension** focuses on the formal and informal structures, rules, and norms that guide the functioning of the CO. This includes the governance mechanisms, organisational structures, and accountability frameworks that ensure transparency, participation, and equitable representation of diverse stakeholders.

The **power dynamics** dimension addresses the power balances/imbbalances among the different actors of a CO. It maps the internal power dynamics that connect the objectives, the functioning and the results of the initiatives of each innovation pilot. It supports the description of how the current decision-making system works and presents information about the formal and informal rules and regulations related to the central topic of the CO.

By considering the political, institutional and power dynamics dimension, the Citizen Observatory can effectively engage with decision-makers, advocate for change, and influence policy processes. It also allows for the creation of robust and inclusive governance mechanisms that promote transparency, accountability, and meaningful participation of citizens in decision-making processes.

4. Does your institution have a participatory law or policy? Explain how it can influence the GREENGAGE IA innovation pilot purpose.

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Q4 Recommendation

<p>5. Has your organisation any gender, inclusion and diversity policies? <i>[Prompt] Explain how they can influence the CO, and if there are any guidelines or recommendations that could be leveraged for the innovation pilot execution and/or CO.</i></p>

Q5 Recommendation

<p>6. Are there any other policies, programmes or plans that can potentially influence the functioning of the CO? Please, identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:</p>
<p>a. Participatory research</p>
<p>b. Climate change</p>
<p>c. Mobility</p>
<p>d. Urban planning</p>

e. Data privacy
f. Connectivity

Q6 Recommendation

7. Identify those governance units / departments within your organisation that have a direct competence within the innovation pilot topics and place them within the hierarchical structure of your organisation.

Q7 Recommendation

8. Does your institution have a Data Governance Department that manages informed consent for participants? <i>[Prompt] Explain if there are any guidelines or recommendations that can be leveraged for the pilot execution.</i>

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Q8 Recommendation

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9. Which stakeholders (including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs and other third sector organisations and citizens) are involved or influence in policy making regarding the topics addressed by the CO objectives?

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Q9 Recommendation

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10. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle³ within your organisation as pilot owner?

[Prompt] Considering that the project lasts three years and different individuals may need to be involved based on the timing of each policy, it will be helpful to identify those individuals so that we can influence the decision-making at different stages of the policy cycle.

a. Agenda setting

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b. Policy formulation

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c. Decision making

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d. Policy implementation

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³ A simplified diagram of the policy cycle can be found here: <https://catalyst.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Unknown.png>

e. Policy evaluation

Q10 Recommendation

11. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe pilot owners can obtain from CO?

Q11 Recommendation

2.3 Technological dimension

GREENGAGE makes available a **set of technological tools called GREEN Engine** to the pilot owners. These are relevant for the innovation pilots since they can be adapted to the specific needs of the use cases, for example for data gathering, processing, analysis and visualisation. It is a set of software tools and applications that will be used to assist pilot owners in meeting their objectives. This toolbox includes a modified version of the Collaborative Environment developed in the INTERLINK H2020 project. The challenge of GREEN Engine is to be able to offer a well-tailored set of technologies needed to achieve each innovation pilot's objectives.

In the initial phases of GREENGAGE, some specific diagnostics have been carried out to determine the needs of each pilot. A first diagnosis is included in deliverable 2.2 "Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 1". There, using the CoReS (Collaborative Requirements Engineering and Stakeholder engagement) methodology, a first diagnosis of needs is presented. The result of this diagnosis is presented in a set of Use Cases and Requirements, which "are an indication of what kind of experiments and data collection can be carried out in GREENGAGE pilots". (Deliverable 2.2, p. 7). On the other hand, deliverable 4.1 "GREEN Engine and manual 1" presents a comprehensive technological analysis of existing technological assets offered by GREENGAGE partners to pilot owners and a breakdown of the requirements to be satisfied for each innovation pilot, as well as the challenges - those factors that cannot be directly addressed using the GREEN Engine technologies.

Another important set of technologies are the **communication technologies and channels**. For each specific CO, the relevance of these technologies focuses on the provision of channels that allow a direct connection between the pilot owner and Citizen Observers, but also among Citizen Observers themselves, allowing people to comfortably share their thoughts, views and experiences with others in an accepting and respectful environment. These communication channels can

include social media, newsletters and events, which will help keep everyone informed about the progress of the project and provide opportunities for feedback.

The decision to choose and adopt any technology, whether existing or new, has social, economic, political, and cultural implications that should be carefully considered. The following questions explore the set of technologies that each innovation pilot envisions to use, and in which manner.

12. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CO?
a. General technologies (e.g., Liveable Neighbourhood platform in the case of Bristol, Argaleo DigiTwin in North Brabant...)
b. Data gathering technologies

Q12 Recommendation

13. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CO objectives with stakeholders? <i>[Prompt] e.g., Face to face, telephone (call or SMS), email, Websites or blogs, social media (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, Discord, etc.), Smartphone Apps (WhatsApp, Viber, Line, etc.), Mass and print media (radio, TV, etc.).</i>
a. Public institutions
b. Academia or groups of experts
c. Private enterprises
d. NGOs or other third sector groups
e. Citizens

Q13 Recommendation

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14. What datasets do you already use to monitor the achievement of the policies that your CO aims to influence? Please consider your answer from question 3.

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Q14 Recommendation

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15. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the CO?

[Prompt] Please bear in mind that even if there are datasets for a specific topic, COs could complement them with more data density for the pilot area (e.g., currently unreached areas).

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Q15 Recommendation

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16. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 14)? Please specify the software tools utilised.

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Q16 Recommendation

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17. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?

Q17 Recommendation

2.4 Public Engagement dimension

To reach many people with a call for participation in the CO, we need to align our calls with local debates and issues that matter for already engaged people. That requires a screening of the local media landscape, researching previous participatory initiatives & talking with mediators that know what issues make people become actively engaged in issues of public concern.

18. Have you any previous experience in organising community-based research or participative initiatives? If yes, please detail: <i>[Prompt] Copy-paste this table as many times as needed</i>
a. Topic of the initiative
b. Communities of citizens involved (e.g., students, elderly people...)
c. Communication channels

Q18 Recommendation

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19. What are local debates and hot issues that are connected or could be connected to your pilot's aspirations?

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Q19 Recommendation

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20. In which kinds of media are local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?

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Q20 Recommendation

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21. Who is expressing these and with which interest?

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Q21 Recommendation

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22. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about?

Q22 Recommendation

23. Are there any other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?

Q23 Recommendation

2.5 Sociodemographic dimension

The information gathered through answering to the requirements of the current dimension will be processed by the CO Coordinators by using an intersectional analysis, which focuses on different social categories (sectionalities) that are interconnected. These social categories are addressed by the breakdown of the indicators that we ask pilot owners to investigate in their official statistical entities.

This analysis considers the characteristics of the population living in the study area and the specific social context of each Pilot Project. It ensures that the COs are suitable and inclusive, promoting participation and effectively carrying out the activities of the innovation pilots. Following the GREENGAGE methodology, it is important to examine the city's population from an intersectional perspective and strive for equality in terms of representation among different groups, including minority groups.

The following indicators should be investigated in the official statistical entities with regards to the delimited innovation pilot area. Since the information provided by the official statistical entities varies among each European country, the segregation or breakdown of the different indicators should be provided according to the available data, in each specific innovation pilot.

- Number of inhabitants.
- Population distribution by:
 - age groups

- gender
- origin
- disability
- Social classes within the innovation pilot area.
- Educational levels disaggregated by gender.

Sociodemographic dimension recommendation

ANNEX B- GREENGAGE Analysis Guide for the Situational Screening Questionnaire

This guide is a document aiming at providing a common understanding on the usefulness of the questionnaire developed for the GREENGAGE IA’s Task 3.1 – Mapping GREENGAGE CO-enabling solution to pilot context. It provides the vision and mission of all the questions included in the mentioned questionnaire, detailing goals, expected findings and general recommendations to be made to the pilot owners. The recommendations generated are meant to guide them through the process of preparing themselves, that is, addressing and making the necessary adjustments on the diverse elements from the dimensions that are relevant for the CO, to set up the CO. The goal of this guide is to support the analysis of the answers provided by the pilot owners, that will be done by the Pilot Support Teams (PSTs). This guide is sufficiently general to allow tailoring the recommendations to the different situations that each pilot owner has, but ensures that a common understanding among its users, and provides a common pathway of what type of recommendations should be finally delivered to the pilot owners.

The following table details the goals, expected findings and general recommendations per each question included in the questionnaire.

2.1 Goals and objectives of the innovation pilots			
Question	Goal of the question	Expected findings	Recommendations
1. Which stakeholders were consulted for the formulation of the objectives and goals of the CO? And why?	To check what stakeholders were considered for the definition of the CO objectives in order to identify them and invite them to become CObs.	Which stakeholders were not consulted?	Reflect on the following: * Is the involvement of these stakeholders important as CObs? * How does this exclusion affect the project's goal? * If the stakeholders that were not consulted are important to reach the CO objectives, map them

<p>2. Who are the potential beneficiaries of the defined CO goals? Please explain what the expected benefits per target group are.</p>	<p>To leverage the expected benefits for each stakeholder as arguments to foster their participation in the communication and engagement strategy, as well as to co-define the specific activities to be done with the different COs and the governance scheme.</p>	<p>*Benefits of specific stakeholders were identified. * Some stakeholders seem to not perceive any benefit from the COs.</p>	<p>* Reflect on potential direct and indirect; short and long-term benefits per each stakeholder type, even if in the first instance the CO didn't seem to cause any on specific stakeholder groups</p>
<p>3. Please identify, according to the specific objectives of your innovation pilot, the national, regional and/or local policies and plans and their targets, that ultimately could be influenced by the results of the CO.</p>	<p>To have a list of the policies and plans that may be influenced by the CO activities and outputs (new data, community-based decision-making, or others)</p>	<p>List of policies and plans that could be influenced by the CO, and their scale (national, regional and local)</p>	<p>To consider the identified policies for the definition of the CO activities and outputs. How could the COs foster policies' implementation? Identify the objectives (within the policy) to which the COs will/could favour</p>
<p>2.2 Political, institutional and power dynamics dimension</p>			
<p>Question</p>	<p>Goal of the question</p>	<p>Expected Findings</p>	<p>Recommendations</p>
<p>4. Does your institution have a participatory law or policy? Explain how it can influence the GREENGAGE IA innovation pilot purpose.</p>	<p>To explore the legal framework about public/citizen participation in relation to the public authority and adhere to it.</p>	<p>The political/legal framework for public participation in the democratic life.</p>	<p>Extract any useful guidelines or best practices to perform the CO participatory activities.</p>
<p>5. Has your organisation any gender, inclusion and diversity policies?</p>	<p>To explore the legal framework about gender, inclusion and diversity policies, adhere to it and potentially foster the achievement of one or more of its objectives through the CO</p>	<p>The political/legal framework for gender, inclusion and diversity</p>	<p>Extract any useful guidelines or best practices to perform the CO participatory activities. Identify the policy(ies) objective(s) or indicator(s) to which the CO could favour</p>

<p>6. Are there any other policies, programmes or plans that can potentially influence the functioning of the CO? Please, identify them and briefly explain how they could interact with the CO. A non-exhaustive list of policy areas is provided for inspiration:</p>	<p>* To have a list of the policies and plans that may be influenced by the CO activities and outputs (new data, community-based decision-making, or others) * To explore the legal framework about other relevant policies and adhere to it.</p>	<p>List of policies and plans that could be influenced by the CO, and their scale (national, regional and local) The political/legal framework for other policy areas that the CO could address or be restricted/promoted by somehow.</p>	<p>To consider the identified policies for the definition of the CO activities and outputs. How could the COs foster policies' implementation? Identify the objectives or indicators (within the policy) to which the COs will/could favour Extract any useful guidelines or best practices to perform the CO activities.</p>
<p>7. Identify those governance units / departments within your organisation that have a direct competence within the innovation pilot topics and place them within the hierarchical structure of your organisation.</p>	<p>*To identify the departments within the pilot owner that should be part of the GREENGAGE CO governance structure, as a starting point to define it internally.</p>	<p>List of governance units/departments of the pilot owner that have relation with the CO objectives and topics</p>	<p>Make sure that the governance units/departments cover all the CO objectives' topics, fields or areas of expertise. You can, for example, align the objectives with the listed governance units/departments in a matrix to explore if this is done. Establish the CO governance structure, including all the relevant governance units/departments identified. Include the persons/units responsible for legislative creation and decision-making, which could act as followers and advisors of the CO process. A CO governance structure should be created, allocating a role/function of the identified governance units / departments within the CO governance structure.</p>

<p>8. Does your institution have a Data Governance Department that manages informed consent for participants?</p>	<p>* To identify the governance unit/department that manages participatory activities with citizens</p>	<p>Identification of the Data Governance Department or the lack of it.</p>	<p>Adhere to the current way of performing activities of the Department, if any, with regards to the personal data management. Include the Data Governance Department in the CO governance structure. Its functions would be to both manage personal data and the data that will be created through the CO and the COBs.</p>
<p>9. Which stakeholders (including public institutions, academia, private businesses, NGOs and other third sector organisations and citizens) are involved in or influence policy making regarding the topics addressed by the CO objectives?</p>	<p>*To identify any other stakeholder that has any degree of influence in policy making in the topics addressed by the CO.</p>	<p>List of stakeholders that influence policy making and in which manner (consultation or lobbying)</p>	<p>Contact them to inform about the project and invite them to join it in any form (COBs or follower of the CO progress)</p>
<p>10. Who has decision-making authority at each step in the policy making cycle within your organisation as pilot owner?</p>	<p>*To identify the persons or governance units that have decision making power in the different steps / phases of the policy lifecycle. These should be informed on the CO progress and achievements, as well as define what type of data and/or activities (to be done by the CO) could be relevant for each step of the policy lifecycle.</p>	<p>List of individuals / governance units per policy lifecycle step / phase.</p>	<p>Involve them in the governance structure (e.g., as advisors or followers)</p>

<p>11. If policies cannot be changed or influenced, what benefits or outcomes do you believe pilot owners can obtain from CO?</p>	<p>* To identify any other benefit for the pilot owner and other stakeholders, different from influencing policies at any step of the policy lifecycle.</p>	<p>List of expected benefits per stakeholder</p>	<p>These benefits could be the basis for co-designing the activities to be done through the CO, as well as to create arguments for involving different types of stakeholders as CObs (i.e., as inputs for the engagement strategy).</p>
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2.3 Technological dimension

Question	Goal of the question	Expected findings	Recommendations
<p>12. What technologies, from your current technological stack, do you envision to use for the CO?</p>	<p>* To identify what technologies, normally used by the pilot owner, could be useful for the deployment and execution of the CO.</p>	<p>Selection of own technologies and GREENGAGE provided technologies and their application/use.</p>	<p>Explore the benefits and needs of aligning these with the GREENGAGE ones. Only tools which add value, allow a CO to be realized, apart to the ones you already have in place</p>
<p>13. What communication technologies and channels would you use for sharing information about the topics addressed by the CO objectives with stakeholders?</p>	<p>* To identify the channels used to establish communication with the different stakeholders about the topics addressed by the CO.</p>	<p>Map of communication channels per stakeholder and communication/message type</p>	<p>Leverage these communication channels to support the creation of the first community of CObs. Explore if the identified communication channels are suitable for all the stakeholders required to become CObs and explore if these still are the best option to communicate with them (in a later stage, during the co-creation workshop to be done in T5.1).</p>
<p>14. What datasets do you already use to monitor the achievement of the policies that your CO aims to influence? Please consider your</p>	<p>* To identify the datasets used for the formulation, implementation and evaluation of policies and their objectives and/or indicators.</p>	<p>Repositories of datasets identified. Means of accessing and querying that data is known.</p>	<p>1. Identify how useful those data sources are for the policy making or monitoring or evaluation or other decision making? 2. How transparent those data sources are in policy-making/evaluation? 3. How accessible</p>

answer from question 3.			those datasets are to GREENGAGE for analysis purposes? and, 4. (this may also be relevant to Q 15) Are there any potential data gaps where GREEN Engine may be able to complement data/information?
15. What datasets are missing and could be covered by the CO?	* With regards to the CO potentialities, identification of the type of and sources of data that could be useful for achieving the CO objectives.	Types of data that the pilot owner expect to obtain from the CO. Sources of data that can be used	Establish dialogue among the GREENGAGE partners and the pilot owners to explore how to access these new data sources (GREENGAGE partners) and how to leverage it (pilot owner). Do pilot owners envisage value (as well as possible exploitation) of new data sets which might be generated through GREEN ENGINE?
16. How do you analyse the identified datasets (from question 14)? Please specify the software tools utilised.	* To identify what types of processing (descriptive/predictive/prescriptive analysis, clustering, statistical analysis, geographical correlation, time-space series analysis) would be most suitable to distil actionable information from the aggregated and correlated data	Concrete map of tools/use cases of a given analytical tool for a specific purpose.	Specify the possible thematic exploration per use case, where data is correlated, visualised, KPIs generated so that decision-makers can leverage from the information distilled. A link with WP6 indicators should be established.
17. In relation to your existing datasets, what data structure and metadata are you using?	* To figure out whether you use internally Excel spreadsheets, JSON files, relational databases, raster images, GIS data	* To know what tools are more suitable to manage these data sources (capture, storage, analysis and exploitation)	Reflect on data volume, formats and ways of accessing and processing such data so that thematic co-explorations can be assembled. Some of these details should be in D1.11 Data management plan and D2.6 technical requirements.
2.4 Public Engagement dimension			
Question	Goal of the question	Expected findings	Recommendations

<p>18. Have you any previous experience in organising community-based research or participative initiatives?</p>	<p>To identify previous participatory initiatives undertaken by the pilot owner in order to leverage already existing assets such as engaged communities and communication channels.</p>	<p>List of participatory initiatives; degree of expertise</p>	<p>If the initiative is related to any of the topics addressed by the CO, to recover the contact data of the engaged community in order to reach them again.</p>
<p>19. What are local debates and hot issues that are connected or could be connected to your pilot's aspirations?</p>	<p>To identify issues that matter locally in order to be mindful whether or not to relate CO objectives to these issues. Avoiding or provoking dispute around these debates (reasonable disputes are important for healthy democratic societies).</p>	<p>The main debates can be related to three areas: * Public administration plans or strategies that are under discussion. * Unresolved needs of the region (tourism, environmental quality, infrastructure) * Issues of public interest that are controversial</p>	<p>Recommendations should aim to conciliate the parties by involving the different actors in the dispute (administrations, private sector, communities). Communication should always be oriented towards mediating between conflicting interests and not aiming to avoid conflicts/tensions. Leverage local debates to create the engagement strategy per stakeholder type.</p>
<p>20. In which kinds of media are these local debates carried out and hot issues expressed?</p>	<p>This helps us to identify the role of local media in the debate, in order to include them appropriately in the mediation. It is relevant to identify possible forms of communication between groups.</p>	<p>The means involved may be: * Official channels * Media outlets (radio, television, etc.) * Social networks and informal channels</p>	<p>Use/leverage the different media channels identified and tailor the call for participation to different audiences' issues.</p>
<p>21. Who is expressing these and with which interest?</p>	<p>* To identify powerful communities of citizens or other stakeholders shaping opinions and influencing policy making.</p>	<p>There may be organised groups or communities that are addressing these issues.</p>	<p>Involve the different groups in participation and dissemination of the pilot. To propose strategies to reconcile and dialogue between different discourses</p>
<p>22. Who is not speaking in these public debates but is the object of what is spoken about?</p>	<p>* To identify possibly excluded groups we seek to address with the GREENGAGE COs.</p>	<p>Some excluded groups could be identified.</p>	<p>To understand better why these groups are excluded and get closer to the forms of dialogue and discourse of these excluded communities.</p>

<p>23. Are there other forms of expression, like public protests that serve as a medium to engage in public debates & hot issues?</p>	<p>Identify communities and associations interested in these issues and discuss and disseminate them.</p>	<p>There could be well-established communities and associations with a well-formed discourse.</p>	<p>If well-established associations are found, invite their participation or avoid conflict with them through dialogue.</p>
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2.5 Sociodemographic dimension

Question	Goal of the question	Expected findings	Recommendations
<p>Number of inhabitants.</p>	<p>Explore the population characteristics in terms of age, gender, origin, disability, social class and educational level in the CO action area.</p>	<p>Socio-demographic statistics provided by the Authoritative Statistical Entity.</p>	<p>The community of CObs should be proportionate to the demographic reality in the CO area. These statistics should be used to define indicators for creating representative communities of CObs.</p>
<p>Population distribution by age</p>			
<p>Population distribution by gender</p>			
<p>Population distribution by origin</p>			
<p>Population distribution by disability</p>			
<p>Social classes within the innovation pilot area.</p>			
<p>Educational levels disaggregated by gender.</p>			